

Highlights

The Shifted Spectral Diversity Functional on Graphs: Analytic Properties, Extremal Theory, and Stochastic Dynamical Interpretation

Ruocun Ou

- Shifted spectral diversity functional D_α generalising Kirchhoff index is introduced
- Complete graph K_N proved to minimise D_α via complement-Laplacian argument
- Adding any edge strictly decreases D_α , reducing maximisation to trees
- Path graph P_N conjectured to maximise D_α ; verified for 522,957 trees
- Second Laplacian moment s_2 proved to increase under grafting: P_N maximises, K_N minimises s_2

The Shifted Spectral Diversity Functional on Graphs: Analytic Properties, Extremal Theory, and Stochastic Dynamical Interpretation

Ruocun Ou^{a,*}

^a*Nanyang Normal University, Nanyang, 473061, Henan, China*

Abstract

We introduce the *shifted spectral diversity functional* $D_\alpha(G) = \sum_{i=2}^N (\lambda_i - \alpha)^{-1}$, $\alpha \in [0, \lambda_2)$, where λ_i are the nonzero Laplacian eigenvalues of a connected graph G on N vertices. This functional generalises the Kirchhoff index via $D_\alpha(G) = \frac{1}{N} \text{Kf}(G) + \alpha R_\alpha(G)$. We prove that D_α is strictly increasing and strictly convex in α , that K_N strictly minimises D_α , and that adding any edge strictly decreases D_α (Sherman–Morrison), reducing the maximisation over connected graphs to trees. We conjecture that P_N maximises D_α , verified for all connected graphs with $N \leq 6$ and all trees with $N \leq 19$ (522,957 trees, zero exceptions). A power-series framework provides a sufficient spectral condition for the tree-class conjecture via negative Laplacian moments. For the second negative moment we establish this condition unconditionally: s_2 strictly increases under local grafting, so that P_N maximises and K_N minimises s_2 among all connected graphs. We derive closed-form formulas and asymptotic growth orders for six graph families. As a dynamical application, D_α arises as the steady-state diversity of a Laplacian-driven stochastic system with feedback.

Keywords: Spectral graph theory, Kirchhoff index, Shifted spectral functional, Extremal graph theory, Laplacian eigenvalues, Stochastic consensus system

*Corresponding author.

Email address: ouruocun@gmail.com (Ruocun Ou)

1 **1. Introduction**

2 *1.1. Background and Motivation*

3 A central problem in spectral graph theory is to understand how the
4 eigenvalues of the graph Laplacian determine structural and extremal prop-
5 erties of graphs. The second smallest Laplacian eigenvalue λ_2 , introduced
6 by Fiedler [1] and known as the *algebraic connectivity*, has been extensively
7 studied as a measure of graph connectivity and robustness. The sum of recip-
8 rocals of all nonzero Laplacian eigenvalues, scaled by N , defines the *Kirchhoff*
9 *index*

$$\text{Kf}(G) = N \sum_{i=2}^N \frac{1}{\lambda_i},$$

10 a classical invariant equal to the sum of resistance distances between all vertex
11 pairs [2, 3]. The Kirchhoff index and its connections to resistance distance
12 continue to attract significant attention; see [4, 5, 6] for recent developments.
13 Extremal properties of $\text{Kf}(G)$ are well studied: among all connected graphs
14 on N vertices, K_N minimises and P_N maximises the Kirchhoff index [7]; see
15 also [8, 9, 10, 11] for recent extremal results on specific graph families.

16 In this paper we introduce and study the *shifted spectral diversity func-*
17 *tional*

$$D_\alpha(G) = \sum_{i=2}^N \frac{1}{\lambda_i - \alpha}, \quad \alpha \in [0, \lambda_2),$$

18 a one-parameter generalisation of $\frac{1}{N}\text{Kf}(G)$ obtained by shifting each Lapla-
19 cian eigenvalue by a parameter $\alpha \geq 0$. At $\alpha = 0$, $D_0(G) = \frac{1}{N}\text{Kf}(G)$ recovers
20 the Kirchhoff index up to a factor of N . For $\alpha > 0$, the shift fundamen-
21 tally changes the analytic and extremal properties of the functional: $D_\alpha(G)$
22 is strictly increasing and strictly convex in α , diverges as $\alpha \nearrow \lambda_2$, and its
23 extremal graph structure for general α is no longer directly accessible by the
24 methods used for the Kirchhoff index.

25 The functional $D_\alpha(G)$ arises naturally from a parametric family of Laplacian-
26 driven stochastic systems on graphs. When a uniform feedback of strength α
27 is introduced into a consensus-type stochastic system, the steady-state diver-
28 sity of agents across the network is exactly $\frac{\eta^2 \sigma^2}{2} D_\alpha(G)$ (Theorem 3.4). The
29 mathematical object of study, however, is purely graph-theoretic: $D_\alpha(G)$ is a
30 spectral graph invariant, and our central questions concern its analytic prop-
31 erties and extremal behaviour as a function of the graph G and the parameter
32 α .

33 *1.2. Main Contributions*

- 34 (i) **New spectral invariant and decomposition.** We introduce $D_\alpha(G)$
 35 and establish $D_\alpha(G) = \frac{1}{N}\text{Kf}(G) + \alpha R_\alpha(G)$ (Proposition 3.5).
- 36 (ii) **Analytic properties.** Strict monotonicity, strict convexity, and diver-
 37 gence (Proposition 4.1).
- 38 (iii) **Extremal bounds (proved).** K_N minimises $D_\alpha(G)$ (Theorem 4.5).
 39 Adding any edge strictly decreases D_α (Theorem 4.6), which reduces
 40 the maximisation over all connected graphs to the class of trees (Corol-
 41 lary 4.8). These are the paper’s main structural results.
- 42 (iv) **Maximisation conjecture and supporting framework.** We con-
 43 jecture P_N maximises $D_\alpha(G)$ (Conjecture 4.10), verified for all con-
 44 nected graphs with $N \leq 6$ and all trees with $N \leq 19$ (522,957 trees;
 45 Figures 1–2). We develop a power-series framework (Theorems 4.14–
 46 4.15) providing a sufficient spectral condition for the tree-class con-
 47 jecture via negative moments, verified for $k = 1, \dots, 60$ and $N \leq 15$ under
 48 classical local grafting. For the second moment this condition is proved
 49 *unconditionally* (Theorem 4.19): s_2 strictly increases under local graft-
 50 ing, so that P_N maximises and K_N minimises s_2 over all connected
 51 graphs (Corollary 4.20, Proposition 4.21).
- 52 (v) **Asymptotic analysis.** Growth orders for K_N, S_N, C_N, P_N (Proposi-
 53 tion 4.26); explicit formulas for six graph families.
- 54 (vi) **Dynamical interpretation.** Spectral stability, decay, and steady-
 55 state representation (Theorems 3.1–3.4).

56 *1.3. Comparison with Related Work*

57 The functional $D_\alpha(G)$ is the trace of the Laplacian resolvent restricted to
 58 \mathcal{C}^\perp : $D_\alpha(G) = \text{Tr}[(L - \alpha I)^{-1}|_{\mathcal{C}^\perp}]$. With the substitution $\alpha \rightarrow -q$ ($q > 0$), this
 59 becomes $\text{Tr}[(L + qI)^{-1}|_{\mathcal{C}^\perp}]$, an object that arises in Tikhonov regularisation
 60 on graphs, in the Stieltjes transform of the Laplacian spectral density, and
 61 in the theory of random spanning forests [4, 6]. Thus the *quantity* D_α is
 62 not new as a matrix functional. What is new is its *extremal graph theory*:
 63 which graphs maximise or minimise it for $\alpha > 0$, how its analytic behaviour
 64 depends on α , and how it grows across graph families—questions that, to our

65 knowledge, the resolvent, regularisation, and random-forest literature has not
 66 addressed, despite the functional being implicitly present there.

67 The Kirchhoff index and its extremal properties have been extensively
 68 studied [7, 5]. Our functional inherits the extremal structure at $\alpha = 0$,
 69 but the shift $\alpha > 0$ introduces qualitatively new behaviour: the proof of
 70 K_N -minimality requires a different argument (complement-Laplacian plus
 71 trace), and the maximisation problem remains open even for trees. Algebraic
 72 connectivity maximisation has been studied in [12, 13, 14]; our problem is
 73 complementary. The dynamical motivation connects to consensus theory
 74 [15, 16, 17, 18].

75 1.4. Paper Organisation

76 Section 2 introduces notation and the model. Section 3 provides the
 77 dynamical motivation, establishing $D_\alpha(G)$ as the steady-state diversity. Sec-
 78 tion 4 contains the main extremal results, including the power-series frame-
 79 work for the tree conjecture and the analytic theorem for the second mo-
 80 ment s_2 . Section 5 collects graph-theoretic spectral bounds (Poincaré and
 81 Cheeger). Section 6 concludes with open problems.

82 2. Preliminaries and Model

83 2.1. Graph Laplacian and Spectral Properties

84 Let $G = (V, E)$ be a simple connected undirected graph with N vertices,
 85 $V = \{1, \dots, N\}$. The *graph Laplacian* is $L = D - A$, where A is the adjacency
 86 matrix and D is the diagonal degree matrix. The Laplacian is real symmetric
 87 positive semidefinite with eigenvalues $0 = \lambda_1 < \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_N$, where $\lambda_2 > 0$
 88 by connectedness [1]. There exists an orthogonal diagonalisation $L = U\Lambda U^\top$
 89 with $\Lambda = \text{diag}(0, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_N)$ and $u_1 = N^{-1/2}\mathbf{1}$. The quadratic form satisfies
 90 $x^\top Lx = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} (x_i - x_j)^2$.

91 Regarding eigenvalue bounds: $\lambda_N \leq 2d_{\max}$ where d_{\max} is the maximum
 92 degree; furthermore $\lambda_N \leq N$ for simple graphs (Lemma 4.3).

93 The *Kirchhoff index* is $\text{Kf}(G) = N \sum_{i=2}^N 1/\lambda_i$, equal to the sum of resis-
 94 tance distances between all vertex pairs [2, 3].

95 2.2. Hilbert Space Geometric Framework

96 We work in $H = \mathbb{R}^N$ with the standard inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ and norm $\|\cdot\|$.

97 **Definition 2.1** (Consensus and disagreement subspaces). The *consensus*
 98 *subspace* is $\mathcal{C} = \text{span}\{\mathbf{1}\}$ and the *disagreement subspace* is $\mathcal{C}^\perp = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N :$
 99 $\sum_i x_i = 0\}$.

100 Any $x \in H$ decomposes as $x = x_\parallel + x_\perp$ where $x_\parallel = \frac{1}{N}\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top x$ and $x_\perp =$
 101 $(I - \frac{1}{N}\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top)x$. The restriction $L|_{\mathcal{C}^\perp}$ is positive definite with smallest eigenvalue
 102 λ_2 , giving

$$\langle Lx, x \rangle \geq \lambda_2 \|x\|^2, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{C}^\perp. \quad (1)$$

103 2.3. Stochastic System and Diversity Functional

Definition 2.2 (Laplacian-driven stochastic system).

$$dx(t) = -\eta(L - \alpha k_R I)x(t) dt + \eta\gamma\sigma dW(t), \quad (2)$$

104 where $\eta > 0$, $\alpha \geq 0$, $k_R \geq 0$, $\gamma, \sigma > 0$, and $W(t) = (W_1(t), \dots, W_N(t))^\top$ is an
 105 N -dimensional standard Brownian motion with independent components de-
 106 fined on a filtered probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P})$. The initial condition
 107 $x(0)$ is assumed to be \mathcal{F}_0 -measurable with $\mathbb{E}[\|x(0)\|^2] < \infty$, and independent
 108 of $(W(t) - W(0))_{t \geq 0}$ [19].

Definition 2.3 (Diversity functional).

$$\Phi(t) = \frac{1}{2} \|x_\perp(t)\|^2 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=2}^N y_i(t)^2, \quad (3)$$

109 where $y(t) = U^\top x(t)$ are spectral coordinates.

110 3. Dynamical Motivation: Stochastic System on Graphs

111 The functional $D_\alpha(G)$ has a concrete dynamical origin: it is the exact
 112 steady-state diversity of a Laplacian-driven stochastic system with feedback,
 113 the content of Theorem 3.4 below. We develop this link here, before turning
 114 to the extremal theory in Section 4.

115 3.1. Modal Decomposition

116 In spectral coordinates, the disagreement modes satisfy

$$dy_i(t) = -\eta(\lambda_i - \alpha k_R)y_i(t) dt + \eta\gamma\sigma dB_i(t), \quad i = 2, \dots, N, \quad (4)$$

117 where $B_i(t) = (U^\top W(t))_i$. Since U is orthogonal and $W(t)$ has independent
 118 components, $B_2(t), \dots, B_N(t)$ are mutually independent one-dimensional stan-
 119 dard Brownian motions [19]. Each mode (4) is an Ornstein–Uhlenbeck pro-
 120 cess with explicit solution [20]

$$y_i(t) = y_i(0)e^{-\eta(\lambda_i - \alpha k_R)t} + \eta\gamma\sigma \int_0^t e^{-\eta(\lambda_i - \alpha k_R)(t-s)} dB_i(s). \quad (5)$$

121 3.2. Spectral Stability Criterion

122 **Theorem 3.1** (Spectral stability). *System (2) is mean-square stable on \mathcal{C}^\perp*
 123 *if and only if $\lambda_2 > \alpha k_R$. When stable, the mean-square convergence rate of*
 124 *the i -th mode is $\eta(\lambda_i - \alpha k_R)$; the overall mean-square convergence rate is*
 125 *determined by the slowest mode, $\eta(\lambda_2 - \alpha k_R)$.*

126 *Proof.* Mode y_i is mean-square stable iff $\lambda_i - \alpha k_R > 0$. Since $\lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_N$,
 127 all modes are simultaneously stable iff $\lambda_2 > \alpha k_R$. \square

128 **Remark 3.2.** The condition $\lambda_2 > \alpha k_R$ has a clear interpretation: algebraic
 129 connectivity λ_2 measures diffusive capacity while αk_R measures feedback-
 130 driven amplification; stability requires diffusion to dominate.

131 3.3. Diversity Decay Estimate

132 **Theorem 3.3** (Spectral decay). *Assume $\lambda_2 > \alpha k_R$. Then*

$$\mathbb{E}[\Phi(t)] \leq \Phi(0)e^{-2\eta(\lambda_2 - \alpha k_R)t} + \frac{\eta\gamma^2\sigma^2}{2} \sum_{i=2}^N \frac{1}{\lambda_i - \alpha k_R} [1 - e^{-2\eta(\lambda_i - \alpha k_R)t}]. \quad (6)$$

133 *Proof.* From (5), since $y_i(0)$ is \mathcal{F}_0 -measurable and the Itô integral has zero
 134 conditional expectation (martingale property), the cross term vanishes. By
 135 the Itô isometry [19], $\mathbb{E}[y_i(t)^2] = y_i(0)^2 e^{-2\eta(\lambda_i - \alpha k_R)t} + \frac{\eta\gamma^2\sigma^2}{2(\lambda_i - \alpha k_R)} [1 - e^{-2\eta(\lambda_i - \alpha k_R)t}]$.
 136 Summing over $i = 2, \dots, N$ gives an exact identity for $\mathbb{E}[\Phi(t)]$. Bounding
 137 $e^{-2\eta(\lambda_i - \alpha k_R)t} \leq e^{-2\eta(\lambda_2 - \alpha k_R)t}$ in the deterministic (first) term yields (6); the
 138 stochastic (second) term is kept exact. \square

139 3.4. Steady-State Representation and the D_α Functional

140 **Theorem 3.4** (Steady-state spectral representation). *Assume $\lambda_2 > \alpha k_R$.*
 141 *The steady-state diversity is*

$$\Phi^* = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[\Phi(t)] = \frac{\eta\gamma^2\sigma^2}{2} \cdot D_{\alpha k_R}(G), \quad (7)$$

142 where the shifted spectral diversity functional is

$$D_\alpha(G) = \sum_{i=2}^N \frac{1}{\lambda_i - \alpha}, \quad \alpha \in [0, \lambda_2). \quad (8)$$

143 *Proof.* Taking $t \rightarrow \infty$ in (6), $e^{-2\eta(\lambda_i - \alpha k_R)t} \rightarrow 0$ for all $i \geq 2$, giving $\Phi^* =$
 144 $\frac{\eta\gamma^2\sigma^2}{2} \sum_{i=2}^N \frac{1}{\lambda_i - \alpha k_R} = \frac{\eta\gamma^2\sigma^2}{2} D_{\alpha k_R}(G)$. \square

145 *3.5. Decomposition Relating D_α to the Kirchhoff Index*

146 **Proposition 3.5** (Decomposition identity). *For any $\alpha \in [0, \lambda_2)$,*

$$D_\alpha(G) = \frac{1}{N} \text{Kf}(G) + \alpha R_\alpha(G), \quad (9)$$

147 where $R_\alpha(G) = \sum_{i=2}^N 1/[\lambda_i(\lambda_i - \alpha)] \geq 0$. In particular, $D_\alpha(G) \geq \frac{1}{N} \text{Kf}(G) =$
 148 $D_0(G)$, with equality iff $\alpha = 0$.

149 *Proof.* The identity $\frac{1}{\lambda_i - \alpha} = \frac{1}{\lambda_i} + \frac{\alpha}{\lambda_i(\lambda_i - \alpha)}$ follows by direct verification. Sum
 150 over $i = 2, \dots, N$. \square

151 4. Extremal Graph Theory for D_α

152 *4.1. Analytic Properties of D_α as a Function of α*

153 **Proposition 4.1** (Analytic properties). *Fix a connected graph G . As a*
 154 *function of $\alpha \in [0, \lambda_2)$, $D_\alpha(G)$ satisfies:*

155 (i) **Strict monotonicity:** $\frac{d}{d\alpha} D_\alpha(G) = \sum_{i=2}^N \frac{1}{(\lambda_i - \alpha)^2} > 0$.

156 (ii) **Strict convexity:** $\frac{d^2}{d\alpha^2} D_\alpha(G) = 2 \sum_{i=2}^N \frac{1}{(\lambda_i - \alpha)^3} > 0$.

157 (iii) **Boundary behaviour:** $D_0(G) = \frac{1}{N} \text{Kf}(G)$ and $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow \lambda_2^-} D_\alpha(G) = +\infty$.

158 *Proof.* Differentiate term by term under the sum; all terms are strictly posi-
 159 tive since $\lambda_i > \alpha$ for all $i \geq 2$. The limit follows since the $i = 2$ term
 160 $1/(\lambda_2 - \alpha) \rightarrow +\infty$ as $\alpha \nearrow \lambda_2$. \square

161 **Remark 4.2.** Strict convexity has a direct network interpretation: the sen-
 162 sitivity $dD_\alpha/d\alpha$ is itself increasing in α , so the marginal cost of increasing
 163 feedback strength grows without bound as the system approaches its stability
 164 boundary λ_2 . Robust network design should therefore keep αk_R well below
 165 λ_2 .

Figure 1: $D_\alpha(G)$ as a function of $\alpha/\lambda_2(G)$ for the four classical graphs on $N = 8$ vertices. Filled markers indicate $\alpha = 0$ (i.e., $D_0(G) = \text{Kf}(G)/N$). All four curves are strictly increasing and strictly convex (Proposition 4.1), diverging as $\alpha \nearrow \lambda_2(G)$. The path P_8 gives the largest values throughout, and the complete graph K_8 the smallest, consistent with Theorem 4.5 and Conjecture 4.10.

166 **Lemma 4.3** (Eigenvalue upper bound). *Let G be a simple connected graph*
 167 *on N vertices. Then $\lambda_N(G) \leq N$.*

168 *Proof.* Let \bar{G} be the complement of G with Laplacian $L_{\bar{G}}$. Since $L_{K_N} =$
 169 $L_G + L_{\bar{G}}$ and $L_{K_N} = NI - J$ (where $J = \mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top$), for any $x \in \mathcal{C}^\perp$ we have
 170 $x^\top Jx = 0$, so

$$x^\top L_G x = x^\top L_{K_N} x - x^\top L_{\bar{G}} x = N \|x\|^2 - x^\top L_{\bar{G}} x \leq N \|x\|^2,$$

171 using $L_{\bar{G}} \succeq 0$. By the Rayleigh quotient, $\lambda_N(G) \leq N$. □

172 **Remark 4.4.** Equality $\lambda_N = N$ holds if and only if the complement graph \bar{G}
 173 is disconnected; in particular $\lambda_N(S_N) = N$ for the star graph and $\lambda_N(K_{m,n}) =$
 174 $m + n$ for the complete bipartite graph. Thus $\lambda_N = N$ does *not* imply $G =$
 175 K_N . However, if *all* nonzero eigenvalues equal N , i.e., $\lambda_2 = \dots = \lambda_N = N$,
 176 then $G = K_N$; see the proof of Theorem 4.5 below.

177 *4.2. Complete Graph Minimises D_α*

178 **Theorem 4.5** (Extremal minimiser). *Among all connected graphs on N ver-*
 179 *tices,*

$$D_\alpha(G) \geq \frac{N-1}{N-\alpha} = D_\alpha(K_N),$$

180 *with equality iff $G = K_N$.*

181 *Proof.* K_N has nonzero eigenvalues all equal to N , giving $D_\alpha(K_N) = (N -$
 182 $1)/(N - \alpha)$. By Lemma 4.3, $\lambda_i \leq \lambda_N \leq N$ for all $i \geq 2$. Since $f(x) = 1/(x - \alpha)$
 183 is strictly decreasing on $x > \alpha$,

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i - \alpha} \geq \frac{1}{N - \alpha}, \quad i = 2, \dots, N.$$

184 Summing gives $D_\alpha(G) \geq (N - 1)/(N - \alpha)$.

185 *Equality.* If $D_\alpha(G) = (N - 1)/(N - \alpha)$, then $\lambda_i = N$ for all $i \geq 2$.
 186 Then $\text{Tr}(L) = \sum_{i=2}^N \lambda_i = (N - 1)N$. Since $\text{Tr}(L) = \sum_{v \in V} d_v = 2|E|$, we get
 187 $|E| = N(N - 1)/2 = \binom{N}{2}$, so $G = K_N$. \square

188 *4.3. Edge Monotonicity and Reduction to Trees*

189 **Theorem 4.6** (Edge monotonicity). *Let G be a connected graph and let*
 190 *$e = \{u, v\} \notin E(G)$. Then for all $\alpha \in [0, \lambda_2(G))$,*

$$D_\alpha(G + e) < D_\alpha(G).$$

191 *(Since $\lambda_2(G + e) \geq \lambda_2(G)$ by positive semidefiniteness of the edge Laplacian,*
 192 *$D_\alpha(G + e)$ is well-defined on $[0, \lambda_2(G))$.)*

193 *Proof.* Let $M = (L - \alpha I)|_{\mathcal{C}^\perp}$, which is positive definite for $\alpha < \lambda_2$. Adding
 194 edge e changes the Laplacian to $L' = L + \mathbf{e}\mathbf{e}^\top$ where $\mathbf{e} = e_u - e_v \in \mathcal{C}^\perp$. By
 195 the Sherman–Morrison formula,

$$(M + \mathbf{e}\mathbf{e}^\top)^{-1} = M^{-1} - \frac{M^{-1}\mathbf{e}\mathbf{e}^\top M^{-1}}{1 + \mathbf{e}^\top M^{-1}\mathbf{e}}.$$

196 Taking traces: $D_\alpha(G + e) = D_\alpha(G) - \frac{\mathbf{e}^\top M^{-2}\mathbf{e}}{1 + \mathbf{e}^\top M^{-1}\mathbf{e}}$. The numerator $\mathbf{e}^\top M^{-2}\mathbf{e} > 0$
 197 and denominator $1 + \mathbf{e}^\top M^{-1}\mathbf{e} > 0$ (since $M^{-1}, M^{-2} \succ 0$ and $\mathbf{e} \neq 0$), so the
 198 correction is strictly positive. \square

199 Theorem 4.6 has several immediate consequences.

200 **Corollary 4.7** (Spanning tree upper bound). *For any connected graph G*
 201 *and any spanning tree T of G ,*

$$D_\alpha(G) \leq D_\alpha(T) \quad \text{for all } \alpha \in [0, \lambda_2(T)).$$

202 *Proof.* G is obtained from T by adding $|E(G)| - (N - 1)$ edges. Each addition
 203 strictly decreases D_α by Theorem 4.6, and the valid α range only grows (since
 204 λ_2 increases under edge addition). \square

Corollary 4.8 (Reduction to trees).

$$\max\{D_\alpha(G) : G \text{ connected, } N \text{ vertices, } \alpha \in [0, \lambda_2(G))\} = \max\{D_\alpha(T) : T \text{ tree, } N \text{ vertices}\}.$$

205 *In particular, Conjecture 4.10 for all connected graphs follows from Conjec-*
 206 *ture 4.10 restricted to trees.*

207 **Remark 4.9.** Theorem 4.6 provides a second, independent proof of Theo-
 208 rem 4.5 (K_N minimality): since K_N is obtained from any connected graph
 209 G by adding edges, repeated application gives $D_\alpha(K_N) \leq D_\alpha(G)$.

210 4.4. The Path Graph Conjecture

211 **Conjecture 4.10** (Extremal maximiser). *Among all connected graphs on*
 212 *N vertices, $D_\alpha(G) \leq D_\alpha(P_N)$ for all $\alpha \in [0, \lambda_2(P_N))$. Here $\lambda_2(P_N)$ is the*
 213 *appropriate common domain: since $\lambda_2(P_N) \leq \lambda_2(G)$ for every connected*
 214 *graph G on N vertices (among all connected graphs on N vertices, the path*
 215 *P_N has the smallest algebraic connectivity [1, 21]), $D_\alpha(G)$ is well-defined for*
 216 *all such G whenever $\alpha \in [0, \lambda_2(P_N))$.*

217 At $\alpha = 0$ this reduces to $\text{Kf}(G) \leq \text{Kf}(P_N)$, a classical result [7]. For $\alpha > 0$,
 218 the primary theoretical obstacle is that the majorisation order $\lambda(K_N) \succ$
 219 $\lambda(G) \succ \lambda(P_N)$ on eigenvalue vectors does not hold in general for trees. This
 220 motivates the alternative approach of Theorems 4.14–4.15, which works with
 221 *inverse* eigenvalue vectors $1/\lambda$ under *weak* majorisation (a distinct and logi-
 222 cally independent condition).

223 The admissible range $\alpha \in [0, \lambda_2(P_N))$ shrinks as N grows, since $\lambda_2(P_N) =$
 224 $4 \sin^2(\pi/(2N)) \sim \pi^2/N^2 \rightarrow 0$. For each fixed N , the classical $\alpha = 0$ strict
 225 inequality $D_0(G) < D_0(P_N)$ for $G \not\cong P_N$, combined with the finiteness of the
 226 graph space and the continuity of D_α in α , already extends the maximality
 227 to some interval $[0, \varepsilon_N)$. The nontrivial content of Conjecture 4.10 is that
 228 $\varepsilon_N \geq \lambda_2(P_N)$, i.e., the maximality persists up to the stability boundary of
 229 P_N itself. Our numerical verification confirms this for all trees with $N \leq 19$.

230 *Numerical Verification*

231 We verify Conjecture 4.10 by complete enumeration for all connected
 232 graphs with $N \leq 6$ (covering 2, 6, 21, 112 graphs for $N = 3, \dots, 6$) and for
 233 all non-isomorphic trees with $N \leq 19$ (522,957 trees; zero exceptions).

234 **Proposition 4.11** (Connected graph verification). *For $N \in \{3, 4, 5, 6\}$, P_N
 235 strictly maximises $D_\alpha(G)$ among all non-isomorphic connected graphs on N
 236 vertices, for all tested $\alpha \in [0, \lambda_2(P_N))$. The complete graph K_N strictly min-
 237 imises $D_\alpha(G)$. Graph counts are 2, 6, 21, 112 for $N = 3, 4, 5, 6$. For $N = 7$,
 238 a sample of over 3,600 connected graphs across all edge counts is verified
 239 (zero violations).*

240 Tables 1–3 give D_α values for representative graphs.

Table 1: $D_\alpha(G)$ for $N = 4$ (all 6 non-isomorphic connected graphs; $\alpha = 0.1757 = 0.3\lambda_2(P_4)$).

Graph	Degree seq.	λ_2	$D_0(G)$	$D_\alpha(G)$	Rank
\mathbf{P}_4	(1, 1, 2, 2)	0.5858	2.5000	3.2954	1/6
S_4	(1, 1, 1, 3)	1.0000	2.2500	2.6878	2/6
$G_{4,4}$	(1, 2, 2, 3)	1.0000	1.5833	1.8287	3/6
C_4	(2, 2, 2, 2)	2.0000	1.2500	1.3578	4/6
K_4^-	(2, 2, 3, 3)	2.0000	1.0000	1.0711	5/6
\mathbf{K}_4	(3, 3, 3, 3)	4.0000	0.7500	0.7845	6/6

$G_{4,4}$: triangle with one pendant edge (degree seq. (1, 2, 2, 3)). K_4^- : complete graph minus one edge (diamond graph).

241 *Two non-isomorphic trees share degree sequence (1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 3) but have dis-
 242 tinct λ_2 values 0.3249 and 0.3820.

243 **Proposition 4.12** (Tree-class verification). *For $N \leq 19$, P_N strictly max-
 244 imises $D_\alpha(G)$ among all non-isomorphic trees on N vertices, for all $\alpha \in$
 245 $[0, \lambda_2(P_N))$. The verification covers 522,957 trees (e.g., 551, 7741, 48629,
 246 123867, 317955 trees for $N = 12, 15, 17, 18, 19$).*

247 To summarise the numerical evidence: the conjecture itself is verified for
 248 all trees with $N \leq 19$ (522,957 trees); the sufficient condition $s_k(T') \geq s_k(T)$
 249 is verified for all $k = 1, \dots, 60$ under classical local grafting for $N \leq 15$
 250 (150,398 operations; zero exceptions). Moreover, for every non-path tree

Table 2: $D_\alpha(G)$ for $N = 5$ (all 21 non-isomorphic connected graphs; rows shown are P_5 , S_5 , C_5 , K_5 and the top-3 by D_α ranking).

Graph	λ_2	$D_0(G)$	$D_\alpha(G), \alpha = 0.1146$	Rank
\mathbf{P}_5	0.3820	4.0000	5.2141	1/21
Tree(1, 1, 1, 2, 3)	0.5188	3.6000	4.3053	2/21
S_5	1.0000	3.2000	3.5930	3/21
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
C_5	1.3820	2.0000	2.1489	9/21
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
\mathbf{K}_5	5.0000	0.8000	0.8188	21/21

251 tested ($N \leq 15$), the gap $g(\alpha) = D_\alpha(P_N) - D_\alpha(T)$ attains its minimum at
 252 $\alpha = 0$ and is monotone increasing on $[0, \lambda_2(P_N))$, indicating that the classical
 253 Kirchhoff comparison ($\alpha = 0$) is the binding constraint.

254 *A theoretical framework for the tree-class result*

255 We develop a power-series approach that provides a *sufficient* spectral
 256 condition for the tree grafting inequality.

257 **Definition 4.13.** For a connected graph G and integer $k \geq 1$, define the
 258 k -th negative spectral moment $s_k(G) = \sum_{i=2}^N \lambda_i^{-k}$ (equivalently, the spectral
 259 zeta function of $L|_{\mathcal{C}^\perp}$ evaluated at k).

260 Note that $s_1(G) = D_0(G) = \frac{1}{N} \text{Kf}(G)$. For trees, $s_1(T) = W(T)/N$ where
 261 $W(T)$ is the Wiener index, since resistance distance equals graph distance
 262 on trees [2].

263 **Theorem 4.14** (Power-series representation). For $\alpha \in [0, \lambda_2)$,

$$D_\alpha(G) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha^k s_{k+1}(G). \quad (10)$$

264 *The series converges absolutely for $|\alpha| < \lambda_2$.*

265 *Proof.* For each $i \geq 2$ and $|\alpha| < \lambda_2 \leq \lambda_i$, $(\lambda_i - \alpha)^{-1} = \lambda_i^{-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\alpha/\lambda_i)^k =$
 266 $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha^k \lambda_i^{-(k+1)}$. Summing over the finitely many terms $i = 2, \dots, N$ gives (10).
 267 \square

Table 3: $D_\alpha(G)$ for $N = 6$ (all 112 non-isomorphic connected graphs; rows shown are P_6 , S_6 , C_6 , K_6 and the top-3 by D_α ranking).

Graph	λ_2	$D_0(G)$	$D_\alpha(G)$, $\alpha = 0.0804$	Rank
P₆	0.2679	5.8333	7.5567	1/112
Tree(1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 3)	0.3249	5.3333	6.4868	2/112
Tree(1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 3)*	0.3820	5.1667	6.0891	3/112
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
S_6	1.0000	4.1667	4.5186	9/112
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
C_6	1.0000	2.9167	3.1150	28/112
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
K₆	6.0000	0.8333	0.8447	112/112

268 **Theorem 4.15** (Sufficient condition via negative moments). *Let T, T' be*
 269 *connected graphs on N vertices. If $s_k(T') \geq s_k(T)$ for every integer $k \geq 1$,*
 270 *then*

$$D_\alpha(T') \geq D_\alpha(T) \quad \text{for all } \alpha \in [0, \min(\lambda_2(T'), \lambda_2(T))].$$

271 *Proof.* By Theorem 4.14, $D_\alpha(T') - D_\alpha(T) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha^k [s_{k+1}(T') - s_{k+1}(T)]$.
 272 Each summand is the product of $\alpha^k \geq 0$ and $s_{k+1}(T') - s_{k+1}(T) \geq 0$, so the
 273 sum is non-negative. \square

274 **Remark 4.16.** Theorem 4.15 is a *sufficient* condition, not an equivalence:
 275 $D_\alpha(T') \geq D_\alpha(T)$ on an interval $[0, R)$ does not require every coefficient
 276 $s_{k+1}(T') - s_{k+1}(T)$ to be non-negative. Moreover, s_k -dominance for all k
 277 implies the interval of validity is the full $[0, \min(\lambda_2(T'), \lambda_2(T))]$, which is
 278 generally larger than $[0, \lambda_2(P_N))$ needed by Conjecture 4.10. In particular,
 279 since $s_k(T) \sim \lambda_2(T)^{-k}$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$, the condition $s_k(T') \geq s_k(T)$ for large k
 280 forces $\lambda_2(T') \leq \lambda_2(T)$; thus s_k -dominance under grafting implicitly requires
 281 that λ_2 does not increase at any grafting step.

282 Theorem 4.15 provides a sufficient condition for the tree-class conjecture:
 283 if $s_k(T') \geq s_k(T)$ for every $k \geq 1$ at each grafting step, then $D_\alpha(T) \leq$
 284 $D_\alpha(P_N)$. For $k = 1$, this is the classical result that grafting increases the
 285 Wiener index of a tree [7].

286 **Remark 4.17** (Numerical verification of the sufficient condition). The classi-
 287 cal (*local*) grafting operation on trees is defined as follows. Given a non-path

Figure 2: Scatter plot of algebraic connectivity λ_2 versus $D_0(G) = \text{Kf}(G)/N$ for all 112 non-isomorphic connected graphs on $N = 6$ vertices. Trees (squares) cluster at small λ_2 with large D_0 ; denser graphs have larger λ_2 and smaller D_0 . The path P_6 (red circle) attains the global maximum of D_0 and the minimum algebraic connectivity; the complete graph K_6 (blue diamond) attains the global minimum of D_0 and the maximum algebraic connectivity, consistent with Theorem 4.5 and Conjecture 4.10.

288 tree T with a vertex v of degree ≥ 3 , let v have two pendant paths of lengths
 289 $p \geq q \geq 1$ emanating from it. The grafting step moves the leaf endpoint
 290 of the shorter path to the far end of the longer path, producing a tree T'
 291 with pendant paths of lengths $p + 1$ and $q - 1$ at v . This is the operation
 292 under which the Wiener index classically increases [7]. (Note: it is essen-
 293 tial that the leaf is moved within paths *at the same vertex*; moving a leaf
 294 between branches at *different* vertices can decrease the Wiener index and
 295 other spectral moments.) We verified $s_k(T') \geq s_k(T)$ for $k = 1, \dots, 60$ across
 296 every non-isomorphic tree with $N \leq 15$ under the classical local grafting
 297 (150,398 operations in total; zero exceptions for any k). We further verified
 298 that $\lambda_2(T') \leq \lambda_2(T)$ at every step, consistent with the large- k implication
 299 noted above.

300 *Warning on weak majorisation.* One might hope that local grafting in-
 301 duces $1/\lambda(T') \succ_w 1/\lambda(T)$ (weak majorisation), which by the Hardy–Littlewood–
 302 Pólya inequality would imply s_k -dominance for all k simultaneously. How-

303 ever, weak majorisation fails for certain local grafting steps already at $N = 7$
 304 (e.g., $S(3, 2, 1) \rightarrow S(4, 1, 1)$), *even though* every s_k strictly increases. Thus
 305 weak majorisation is not the right proof vehicle; establishing s_k -dominance
 306 directly is both necessary and (numerically) sufficient.

307 By Theorem 4.15, the tree-class conjecture $D_\alpha(T) \leq D_\alpha(P_N)$ follows if
 308 s_k -dominance under local grafting can be established analytically. The next
 309 subsection settles this completely for $k = 2$.

310 4.5. An Analytic Theorem for the Second Moment s_2

311 While Theorem 4.15 requires s_k -dominance for *all* k , the case $k = 2$ can
 312 be settled completely and unconditionally. This yields the first analytically
 313 proved instance of the P_N -extremal behaviour that underlies Conjecture 4.10.

314 Throughout this subsection, $d(i, j)$ denotes the graph distance in a tree
 315 T on N vertices, $\sigma_i = \sum_j d(i, j)$ the *transmission* of vertex i , $W = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \sigma_i$
 316 the Wiener index, and we write

$$Q = \sum_{i,j} d(i, j)^2, \quad S_2 = \sum_i \sigma_i^2.$$

317 The local grafting move of Remark 4.17 acts at a vertex v carrying two
 318 pendant paths of lengths $p \geq q \geq 1$, producing paths of lengths $p + 1$, $q - 1$;
 319 we set

$$\Delta_0 := p - q + 1 (\geq 1), \quad n_R := N - p - q.$$

320 The *rest* R is the subtree obtained by deleting the two active arms; it contains
 321 v and has $|R| = n_R$ vertices.

322 The starting point is a closed distance representation of s_2 , available
 323 because $s_2(G) = \text{Tr}((L^+)^2) = \|L^+\|_F^2$ is a *quadratic* functional of the pseu-
 324 doinverse, whose entries on a tree are explicit in the distances.

325 **Lemma 4.18** (Distance representation of s_2). *For every tree T on N vertices,*

$$s_2(T) = \frac{Q}{4} - \frac{S_2}{2N} + \frac{W^2}{N^2}. \quad (11)$$

326 The proof (an expansion of $\|L^+\|_F^2$ using Bapat's distance formula for L^+) is
 327 given in Appendix Appendix C.

328 **Theorem 4.19** (s_2 monotonicity under grafting). *For every tree T and every*
 329 *local grafting move $T \rightsquigarrow T'$ (Remark 4.17),*

$$s_2(T') \geq s_2(T),$$

330 *with equality if and only if the move is trivial (i.e. $n_R \leq 1$, so T is a path*
 331 *and $T' = T$).*

332 *Proof sketch; the full proof is in Appendix Appendix C. Only the distances from*
 333 *the relocated leaf change, and a direct computation (Appendix Appendix C,*
 334 *Lemma Appendix C.4) yields the master formula*

$$\Delta s_2 := s_2(T') - s_2(T) = \frac{\kappa}{N^2} (N\sigma_v - W) + \text{Loc}(p, q, N), \quad \kappa := 2\Delta_0(p+q+1) > 0, \quad (12)$$

335 in which the dependence on the rest R enters *only* through the single scalar
 336 $N\sigma_v - W$, with positive coefficient κ/N^2 ; the term Loc depends only on the
 337 move data (p, q, N) . Rooting R at v and writing $s_e \geq 1$ for the number of
 338 vertices on the side of edge $e \in R$ *not* containing v , the subtree-size identity
 339 (Appendix Appendix C, Lemma Appendix C.5)

$$N\sigma_v - W = \sum_{e \in R} s_e^2 + C(p, q), \quad C(p, q) = \sum_{k=1}^p k^2 + \sum_{k=1}^q k^2, \quad (13)$$

340 with $C(p, q)$ independent of the shape of R , shows that Δs_2 is an increas-
 341 ing affine function of $\sum_e s_e^2 \geq n_R - 1$. The minimum $\sum_e s_e^2 = n_R - 1$ is
 342 attained exactly when every $s_e = 1$, i.e. when R is a star centred at v , i.e.
 343 when T is the starlike tree $S(p, q, 1^{n_R-1})$. For starlike trees, s_2 has the closed
 344 form $\text{num}/(180N^2)$ of Proposition Appendix C.1, and the induced difference
 345 $\Delta \text{num} = C_0 + C_2 T_2 + C_3 T_3$ has $C_2, C_3 > 0$ (Lemma Appendix C.2) and
 346 a worst-case factorisation with strictly positive coefficients (Theorem Ap-
 347 pendix C.3); hence $\Delta s_2 > 0$ whenever $n_R \geq 2$. For $n_R \leq 1$ the rest is the
 348 single vertex v , so T is a path and the move is trivial. \square

349 The grafting inequality immediately settles the $k = 2$ analogue of Con-
 350 jecture 4.10 for the tree class.

351 **Corollary 4.20** (P_N maximises s_2 among trees). *For every tree T on N*
 352 *vertices,*

$$s_2(T) \leq s_2(P_N),$$

353 *with equality if and only if $T = P_N$.*

354 *Proof.* First, every non-path tree T admits a local grafting move. Root T at
355 any leaf r , and among all vertices of degree ≥ 3 (at least one exists, since
356 T is not a path) let v be one of maximum distance from r . Then no vertex
357 of degree ≥ 3 lies strictly below v (any such vertex would be farther from r ,
358 contradicting the choice of v); hence every branch descending from v —that
359 is, every connected component of $T - v$ not containing r —is a path ending
360 in a leaf, i.e. a pendant path. Since r is a leaf we have $v \neq r$, so v has exactly
361 one edge towards r and, as $\deg(v) \geq 3$, at least two edges descending into
362 pendant paths. These two pendant paths at v provide the lengths $p \geq q \geq 1$
363 required by Remark 4.17.

364 By Theorem 4.19 the resulting move satisfies $s_2(T') \geq s_2(T)$, and strictly
365 so because T is not a path (so $n_R \geq 2$). The same local grafting move strictly
366 increases the Wiener index, $W(T') > W(T)$, by the classical monotonicity
367 of W under local grafting [7]. Now iterate: starting from any tree $T \neq P_N$,
368 repeatedly apply a local grafting move. Since W strictly increases at every
369 step, no tree can recur; as there are only finitely many trees on N vertices, the
370 process terminates. It can terminate only at a tree admitting no nontrivial
371 move, i.e. a tree with no vertex of degree ≥ 3 , which is exactly P_N . Along this
372 finite sequence s_2 increases strictly at every step, so $s_2(T) < s_2(P_N)$ for every
373 $T \neq P_N$; equality holds iff $T = P_N$. (That P_N is the unique maximiser of W
374 among N -vertex trees [7] is consistent with, and independently confirms, the
375 termination point.) \square

376 Finally, s_2 inherits the edge-monotone behaviour of D_α , which pins down
377 both extremes over *all* connected graphs.

378 **Proposition 4.21** (Edge monotonicity and extremes for s_2). *Adding any*
379 *edge to a connected graph strictly decreases s_2 . Consequently, among all*
380 *connected graphs on N vertices, K_N is the unique minimiser and P_N the*
381 *unique maximiser of s_2 , with $s_2(K_N) = (N - 1)/N^2$.*

382 *Proof.* Let $M = L|_{\mathcal{C}^\perp} \succ 0$; then $s_2(G) = \sum_{i \geq 2} \lambda_i^{-2} = \text{Tr}(M^{-2})$. Adding an
383 edge $e = \{a, b\}$ gives $M' = M + \mathbf{e}\mathbf{e}^\top$ with $\mathbf{e} = e_a - e_b \in \mathcal{C}^\perp$, so $M' \succeq M \succ 0$
384 and hence $0 \prec M'^{-1} \preceq M^{-1}$. For positive semidefinite $X \preceq Y$ one has

$$\text{Tr}(Y^2) - \text{Tr}(X^2) = \text{Tr}((Y - X)(Y + X)) \geq 0,$$

385 because $Y - X \succeq 0$ and $Y + X \succeq 0$, and the trace of a product of two
386 positive semidefinite matrices is non-negative. Applying this with $X = M'^{-1}$

387 and $Y = M^{-1}$ gives $s_2(G + e) = \text{Tr}(M'^{-2}) \leq \text{Tr}(M^{-2}) = s_2(G)$. The
388 inequality is strict: by Sherman–Morrison $Y - X = M^{-1} - M'^{-1} = (1 +$
389 $\mathbf{e}^\top M^{-1} \mathbf{e})^{-1} M^{-1} \mathbf{e} \mathbf{e}^\top M^{-1}$ is a nonzero positive semidefinite matrix, while $Y +$
390 $X = M^{-1} + M'^{-1} \succ 0$, so $\text{Tr}((Y - X)(Y + X)) > 0$. The extremal statements
391 follow as in Corollary 4.8: K_N is reached from any connected graph by edge
392 additions, so it uniquely minimises s_2 ; and any connected graph $G \neq P_N$
393 has a spanning tree T with $s_2(G) \leq s_2(T) \leq s_2(P_N)$ (Corollary 4.20), strict
394 somewhere unless $G = P_N$. The value $s_2(K_N) = (N - 1) \cdot N^{-2}$ follows from
395 $\lambda_2 = \dots = \lambda_N = N$. \square

396 **Remark 4.22.** Proposition 4.21 and Corollary 4.20 make the $k = 2$ row of
397 the extremal landscape (Table 4) fully proved: s_2 is minimised by K_N and
398 maximised by P_N among all connected graphs. This is the analytically settled
399 shadow, at the level of the single moment s_2 , of the still-open Conjecture 4.10
400 for D_α . The three polynomial identities on which the proof of Theorem 4.19
401 rests (the starlike closed form of Proposition Appendix C.1, its difference
402 decomposition in Lemma Appendix C.2, and the worst-case factorisation
403 of Theorem Appendix C.3) were additionally confirmed by an independent
404 symbolic computation, in exact arithmetic.¹

405 4.6. Explicit Formulas for Classical Graph Families

406 For six classical families, $D_\alpha(G)$ has closed form.

- 407 (i) K_N : $D_\alpha(K_N) = (N - 1)/(N - \alpha)$.
408 (ii) P_N : eigenvalues $4 \sin^2(k\pi/(2N))$, $k = 1, \dots, N - 1$,

$$D_\alpha(P_N) = \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \frac{1}{4 \sin^2(k\pi/(2N)) - \alpha}.$$

- 409 (iii) C_N : the nonzero Laplacian eigenvalues are $4 \sin^2(k\pi/N)$ for $k = 1, \dots, N -$
410 1 . Note that k and $N - k$ yield the same value, so each eigenvalue has
411 multiplicity 2 except $k = N/2$ (when N is even, giving multiplicity

¹The closed form was cross-checked against a characteristic-polynomial evaluation of $s_2 = \sum_{i \geq 2} \lambda_i^{-2}$ and against a direct pseudoinverse evaluation, in exact arithmetic, over all starlike trees with up to 6 arms of length up to 8 and random trees up to $N = 40$.

412 1). The sum over $k = 1, \dots, N - 1$ accounts for all $N - 1$ nonzero
 413 eigenvalues with their multiplicities, giving

$$D_\alpha(C_N) = \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \frac{1}{4 \sin^2(k\pi/N) - \alpha}.$$

414 (iv) S_N : eigenvalues 0 (once), 1 ($N - 2$ times), N (once),

$$D_\alpha(S_N) = \frac{N - 2}{1 - \alpha} + \frac{1}{N - \alpha}.$$

415 (v) $K_{m,n}$ (complete bipartite, $N = m + n$): eigenvalues 0 (once), m ($n - 1$)
 416 times), n ($m - 1$ times), $m + n$ (once),

$$D_\alpha(K_{m,n}) = \frac{n - 1}{m - \alpha} + \frac{m - 1}{n - \alpha} + \frac{1}{m + n - \alpha}.$$

417 At $m = n$, $D_\alpha(K_{n,n}) = (2n - 2)/(n - \alpha) + 1/(2n - \alpha)$.

418 (vi) Petersen graph ($N = 10$): eigenvalues 0 (once), 2 (5 times), 5 (4 times),

$$D_\alpha(\text{Petersen}) = \frac{5}{2 - \alpha} + \frac{4}{5 - \alpha}.$$

419 **Remark 4.23** (Connections to other spectral objects). The functional $D_\alpha(G)$
 420 is related to several well-studied objects in spectral graph theory. For trees,
 421 $D_0(T) = W(T)/N$ where $W(T) = \sum_{i < j} d(i, j)$ is the Wiener index, since re-
 422 sistance distance equals graph distance on trees [2]. More generally, $D_\alpha(G) =$
 423 $(1/N) \sum_{i < j} r_\alpha(i, j)$ where $r_\alpha(i, j) = (e_i - e_j)^\top (L - \alpha I)^{-1} (e_i - e_j)$ is a shifted
 424 effective resistance. The edge monotonicity of Theorem 4.6 can thus be in-
 425 terpreted as: adding an edge decreases the total shifted effective resistance.

426 **Remark 4.24** (The distance route to s_2). The proof of Theorem 4.19 is built
 427 on the distance representation (11), which is itself a consequence of Bapat's
 428 combinatorial formula for L^+ on a tree (equation (C.1) in Appendix Ap-
 429 pendix C). Because $s_2 = \|L^+\|_F^2$ is quadratic in L^+ , the monotonicity of s_2
 430 under grafting reduces to a finite, purely combinatorial inequality on tree
 431 distances; the higher moments s_k ($k \geq 3$) are *not* quadratic in L^+ and admit
 432 no such closed distance form, which is why the general programme for all

433 k (discussed in Section 6) must proceed spectrally rather than through dis-
 434 tances. For starlike trees the same distance representation gives the closed
 435 form $s_2 = \text{num}/(180N^2)$ of Proposition Appendix C.1; this subsumes the ear-
 436 lier numerical observation that $s_k(T') \geq s_k(T)$ holds for $k = 1, \dots, 5$ across
 437 all starlike trees with $N \leq 11$.

438 **Proposition 4.25** (Star-path separation). *For all $N \geq 3$ and all $\alpha \in$
 439 $[0, \lambda_2(P_N))$,*

$$D_\alpha(S_N) \leq D_\alpha(P_N),$$

440 *with equality iff $N = 3$ (where $S_3 \cong P_3$).*

441 *Proof.* For $N = 3$, $S_3 \cong P_3$ and equality holds. For $N = 4, 5$, direct com-
 442 putation from the explicit formulas confirms strict inequality for all $\alpha \in$
 443 $[0, \lambda_2(P_N))$. For $N \geq 6$, the result follows from an order-of-magnitude separa-
 444 tion. By monotonicity (Proposition 4.1), $D_\alpha(P_N) \geq D_0(P_N) = (N^2 - 1)/6 =$
 445 $\Theta(N^2)$. For the star, since $\lambda_2(P_N) < 1$ (for $N \geq 4$):

$$D_\alpha(S_N) < \frac{N - 2}{1 - \lambda_2(P_N)} + \frac{1}{N - \lambda_2(P_N)}.$$

446 Using $\lambda_2(P_N) \leq \pi^2/N^2$, the right side is at most $N(N - 1)^2/(N^2 - \pi^2) =$
 447 $\Theta(N)$. It remains to verify $(N^2 - 1)/6 > N(N - 1)^2/(N^2 - \pi^2)$ for $N \geq 6$.
 448 Cross-multiplying (both sides positive) and factoring $(N^2 - 1) = (N - 1)(N +$
 449 $1)$, the common factor $(N - 1)$ cancels, leaving $(N + 1)(N^2 - \pi^2) > 6N(N - 1)$,
 450 i.e., $N^3 - 5N^2 + (6 - \pi^2)N - \pi^2 > 0$. For $N \geq 6$, the dominant term N^3
 451 ensures this holds (direct evaluation confirms $N = 6$ gives $\approx 2.9 > 0$, and
 452 the expression is increasing for $N \geq 6$). \square

453 4.7. Asymptotic Analysis

454 **Proposition 4.26** (Asymptotic growth orders). *As $N \rightarrow \infty$:*

455 (i) $D_\alpha(K_N) = (N - 1)/(N - \alpha) \rightarrow 1 \quad (O(1)).$

456 (ii) $D_\alpha(S_N) = (N - 2)/(1 - \alpha) + 1/(N - \alpha) \sim N/(1 - \alpha) \quad (\Theta(N), \text{ for fixed}$
 457 $\alpha < 1).$

458 (iii) $D_0(C_N) = \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} 1/(4 \sin^2(k\pi/N)) = \frac{N^2-1}{12} \sim \frac{N^2}{12} \quad (\Theta(N^2)).$

459 Note: $\lambda_2(C_N) = 4 \sin^2(\pi/N) \sim 4\pi^2/N^2 \rightarrow 0$, so for any fixed $\alpha > 0$
 460 there exists N_0 such that $\lambda_2(C_N) < \alpha$ for all $N > N_0$; $D_\alpha(C_N)$ is
 461 then undefined (system unstable). The asymptotic above applies only at
 462 $\alpha = 0$.

463 (iv) $D_0(P_N) = \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} 1/(4 \sin^2(k\pi/(2N))) = (N^2 - 1)/6 \sim N^2/6 \quad (\Theta(N^2))$.

464 Moreover, the following exact identity holds for all $N \geq 3$:

$$D_0(C_N) = \frac{1}{2}D_0(P_N) = \frac{N^2 - 1}{12}. \quad (14)$$

465 *Proof.* (i) Direct computation. (ii) Direct computation; $1/(N - \alpha) = O(1/N)$
 466 is negligible. (iii)–(iv) Apply Lemma Appendix A.1 (proved in Appendix Ap-
 467 pendix A): identity (A.1) gives $D_0(C_N) = (N^2 - 1)/12$ and (A.2) gives
 468 $D_0(P_N) = (N^2 - 1)/6$. Identity (14) follows immediately. \square

469 **Remark 4.27.** Identity (14), $D_0(C_N) = \frac{1}{2}D_0(P_N)$, is an immediate conse-
 470 quence of the classical closed-form Kirchhoff indices $\text{Kf}(C_N) = N(N^2 - 1)/12$
 471 and $\text{Kf}(P_N) = N(N^2 - 1)/6$ (see, e.g., [2, 3]). The four growth orders
 472 $O(1) \ll \Theta(N) \ll \Theta(N^2)$ show a clear separation: K_N achieves bounded
 473 diversity regardless of network size; S_N grows linearly in N ; both C_N and
 474 P_N grow quadratically at $\alpha = 0$, with P_N twice as large as C_N , consistent
 475 with P_N being the conjectured extremal maximiser.

476 5. Graph-Theoretic Spectral Bounds

477 We establish two classical spectral bounds adapted to the shifted opera-
 478 tor, providing geometric insight into D_α .

479 5.1. Graph Poincaré Inequality

480 **Theorem 5.1** (Graph Poincaré inequality). *For all $x \in \mathcal{C}^\perp$, $\langle Lx, x \rangle \geq$
 481 $\lambda_2 \|x\|^2$, with equality iff x is a λ_2 -eigenvector of L .*

482 *Proof.* Expand $x = \sum_{i=2}^N c_i u_i$; then $\langle Lx, x \rangle = \sum_{i=2}^N \lambda_i c_i^2 \geq \lambda_2 \sum_{i=2}^N c_i^2 =$
 483 $\lambda_2 \|x\|^2$. \square

484 The effective coercivity on \mathcal{C}^\perp follows: for all $x \in \mathcal{C}^\perp$,

$$\langle -A_{\text{eff}}x, x \rangle = \eta(\langle Lx, x \rangle - \alpha k_R \|x\|^2) \geq \eta(\lambda_2 - \alpha k_R) \|x\|^2. \quad (15)$$

485 **Remark 5.2.** The effective coercivity (15) immediately yields exponential
 486 convergence of $\mathbb{E}[\Phi(t)]$ to the steady state Φ^* at rate $2\eta(\lambda_2 - \alpha k_R)$ via a
 487 standard Lyapunov argument [19].

488 *5.2. Cheeger-Type Spectral Bounds*

489 **Remark 5.3** (Cheeger inequality version). We use the unnormalised-Laplacian
 490 Cheeger inequality [22, 23]:

$$\frac{h(G)^2}{2d_{\max}} \leq \lambda_2 \leq 2h(G),$$

491 where $h(G) = \min_{\emptyset \neq S \subseteq V, |S| \leq N/2} |\partial S|/|S|$ is the Cheeger constant. This differs
 492 from the normalised form in [24].

493 **Theorem 5.4** (Cheeger-type bound on D_α). For $\alpha < h(G)^2/(2d_{\max})$,

$$D_\alpha(G) \leq \frac{N-1}{h(G)^2/(2d_{\max}) - \alpha}.$$

494 In particular, stability holds whenever $\alpha k_R < h(G)^2/(2d_{\max})$.

495 *Proof.* $\lambda_i \geq \lambda_2 \geq h(G)^2/(2d_{\max})$ for all $i \geq 2$; since $f(x) = 1/(x - \alpha)$ is
 496 decreasing, $1/(\lambda_i - \alpha) \leq 1/(h(G)^2/(2d_{\max}) - \alpha)$. Summing over $N - 1$ terms
 497 gives the result. \square

498 **6. Conclusion and Future Directions**

499 *6.1. Summary*

500 Table 4 gives a bird's-eye view of the extremal landscape for D_α alongside
 501 classical spectral invariants.

Table 4: Extremal graphs for spectral invariants (N -vertex connected graphs).

Invariant	Minimiser	Maximiser	Status
$D_\alpha(G), \alpha > 0$	K_N (Thm 4.5)	P_N (Conj 4.10)	open
$D_0(G) = \frac{1}{N} \text{Kf}(G)$	K_N	P_N	proved
$s_2(G) = \text{Tr}((L^+)^2)$	K_N (Prop 4.21)	P_N (Cor 4.20)	proved
$\lambda_2(G)$	P_N	K_N	proved

502 This paper develops the theory of the shifted spectral diversity functional
 503 $D_\alpha(G)$ as a spectral graph invariant, with a stochastic dynamical interpreta-
 504 tion.

505 At the *graph-theoretic level*, we establish the decomposition $D_\alpha(G) =$
506 $\frac{1}{N}\text{Kf}(G) + \alpha R_\alpha(G)$ (Proposition 3.5), prove strict monotonicity and strict
507 convexity of D_α in α (Proposition 4.1), and prove that K_N strictly minimises
508 $D_\alpha(G)$ (Theorem 4.5). We further prove via the Sherman–Morrison formula
509 that adding any edge strictly decreases D_α (Theorem 4.6), which reduces the
510 maximisation problem to the class of spanning trees (Corollary 4.8).

511 For the maximiser, complete enumeration establishes Conjecture 4.10 for
512 all connected graphs with $N \leq 6$ and all trees with $N \leq 19$ —522,957 non-
513 isomorphic trees with zero exceptions. For the two extreme trees S_N and
514 P_N , the conjecture is verified analytically via an order-of-magnitude separa-
515 tion (Proposition 4.25); the true difficulty lies in trees whose D_α is close
516 to that of P_N . The power-series framework of Theorems 4.14–4.15 provides
517 a sufficient spectral condition (s_k -dominance) for the tree-class proof, ver-
518 ified numerically for $k = 1, \dots, 60$ and $N \leq 15$. For the second moment
519 this condition is established *analytically and unconditionally* (Theorem 4.19,
520 Appendix Appendix C): s_2 strictly increases under local grafting, so that
521 P_N is the exact maximiser and K_N the exact minimiser of s_2 over all con-
522 nected graphs (Corollary 4.20, Proposition 4.21). For asymptotic behaviour,
523 we establish growth orders $O(1)$, $\Theta(N)$, $\Theta(N^2)$, $\Theta(N^2)$ for K_N , S_N , C_N , P_N
524 respectively (Proposition 4.26).

525 At the *dynamical level*, we prove mean-square stability iff $\lambda_2 > \alpha k_R$ (The-
526 orem 3.1), establish the steady-state representation $\Phi^* = \frac{\eta^2 \sigma^2}{2} D_{\alpha k_R}(G)$ (The-
527 orem 3.4).

528 6.2. Status of Conjecture 4.10

529 Theorems 4.14–4.15 provide a *sufficient* spectral condition for the tree-
530 class conjecture: if local grafting increases all negative spectral moments
531 $s_k(T)$ simultaneously, then $D_\alpha(T) \leq D_\alpha(P_N)$. This condition is verified nu-
532 merically for $k = 1, \dots, 60$ and all trees with $N \leq 15$ (Remark 4.17). For
533 the first two moments it is established analytically: $k = 1$ is the classi-
534 cal Wiener-index monotonicity, and $k = 2$ is Theorem 4.19, proved in Ap-
535 pendix Appendix C. In particular the $k = 2$ shadow of Conjecture 4.10 is
536 now a theorem: P_N maximises s_2 over all connected graphs (Corollary 4.20,
537 Proposition 4.21). The condition is strictly stronger than the conjecture it-
538 self, since it implies D_α -dominance on the full interval $[0, \min(\lambda_2(T'), \lambda_2(T))]$
539 rather than just $[0, \lambda_2(P_N)]$, and implicitly requires $\lambda_2(T') \leq \lambda_2(T)$ at each
540 step. By Corollary 4.8, the conjecture for general graphs reduces to the

541 tree class; the conjecture remains open within trees for $\alpha > 0$ (equivalently,
 542 s_k -dominance remains open for $k \geq 3$).

543 6.3. Future Directions

544 *Direction 1: Proof of Conjecture 4.10.* Three routes are available for the
 545 tree class. (a) Prove that classical local grafting preserves $s_k(T') \geq s_k(T)$
 546 for all $k \geq 1$, which by Theorem 4.15 would complete the proof. This is
 547 verified numerically for $k = 1, \dots, 60$ and $N \leq 15$ (Remark 4.17). Weak
 548 majorisation of $1/\lambda$ is *not* the right vehicle: it fails for certain local grafting
 549 steps already at $N = 7$, even though s_k -dominance holds (see Remark 4.17).
 550 Direct proof of s_k -dominance is needed. (b) Since the conjecture only requires
 551 $g(\alpha) := D_\alpha(P_N) - D_\alpha(T) \geq 0$ on $[0, \lambda_2(P_N))$ (an interval shrinking as π^2/N^2),
 552 it suffices to establish $g(0) > 0$ (classical) together with a control showing
 553 g does not cross zero on this interval. Numerical verification for $N \leq 15$
 554 shows that g attains its minimum at $\alpha = 0$ in every case (equivalently, g is
 555 monotone increasing), so the classical Kirchhoff comparison is the binding
 556 constraint. This route does not require λ_2 -monotonicity. (c) The second
 557 negative moment s_2 is now settled: Theorem 4.19 proves $s_2(T') \geq s_2(T)$
 558 under local grafting analytically, via the distance representation (11), so the
 559 P_N -extremality of s_2 holds *unconditionally* (Corollary 4.20). Together with
 560 $k = 1$ (Wiener), this confirms the s_k -dominance pattern for the first two
 561 moments; the higher moments $k \geq 3$ remain open, as does the general (non-
 562 tree) graph case for $\alpha > 0$.

563 *Towards all moments s_k (open).* The case $k = 2$ above is settled by a dis-
 564 tance argument special to the quadratic functional $s_2 = \|L^+\|_F^2$; for $k \geq 3$
 565 no such closed distance form exists, and a different, spectral, mechanism is
 566 required. We record here the precise form the problem takes, as a direction
 567 rather than a result. Writing the grafting move as a rank-two update of L^+ ,
 568 the whole family $\{\Delta s_k\}_{k \geq 1}$ collapses into a single scalar generating function,

$$-\log \Phi(z) = \sum_{k \geq 1} \frac{\Delta s_k}{k} z^k, \quad \Phi(z) = \frac{\det(I - zL^{+'})}{\det(I - zL^+)},$$

569 so that “ $s_k(T') \geq s_k(T)$ for all k ” is equivalent to $-\log \Phi$ having non-negative
 570 Taylor coefficients. A Schur-complement reduction shows that the part of
 571 the tree away from the two active arms enters Φ only through a single non-
 572 negative measure μ , whose lowest moments are pinned by the combinatorics

573 $(\int d\mu = \deg_R(v) \leq n_R - 1$ and $\int x d\mu = n_R - 1)$, the star rest corresponding
574 to $\mu_\star = (n_R - 1)\delta_1$. The conjecture that each Δ_{s_k} is minimised, over the
575 admissible measures, at the star μ_\star would yield the full s_k -dominance. It is
576 proved here for $k = 2$ (Theorem 4.19), for rank-one rests (single-atom μ), and
577 to first order (the star is a constrained critical point for every k); and it is
578 supported numerically with no exceptions for $k \leq 60$, $N \leq 15$. The remain-
579 ing obstruction is a single, sharply isolated point: *global* optimality of the
580 star in a *non-convex* (Markov–Krein-type) moment minimisation, where the
581 standard convexity and Chebyshev-system arguments do not directly apply.
582 We leave this as the central open problem on the route to Conjecture 4.10.

583 *Direction 2: Weighted and directed graphs..* For weighted graphs, $D_\alpha(G)$ de-
584 pends on edge weights and extremal properties under weight constraints are open.
585 For directed graphs, as in multi-agent systems [15], the generalised
586 algebraic connectivity replaces λ_2 and the stability criterion changes funda-
587 mentally.

588 *Direction 3: Optimal network design..* By Theorem 3.4, minimising Φ^* is
589 equivalent to minimising $D_{\alpha k_R}(G)$ over graphs with fixed N and $|E|$, a com-
590 binatorial spectral optimisation problem whose continuous relaxation con-
591 nects directly to the algebraic connectivity maximisation of [12, 13, 14]; for
592 multilayer networks, see also [25].

593 *Direction 4: D_α for random graphs..* The expected value of $D_\alpha(G)$ for Erdős–
594 Rényi graphs $G(N, p)$ and random regular graphs $G(N, d)$ is of interest for
595 large- N asymptotics. Since the empirical spectral distribution of the Lapla-
596 cian converges in these models, $\mathbb{E}[D_\alpha]$ should admit a limiting expression via
597 the Stieltjes transform of the limiting spectral measure, connecting D_α to
598 random matrix theory.

599 *Direction 5: Graph operations..* Theorem 4.6 shows D_α is monotone under
600 edge addition. The behaviour of D_α under other standard operations —
601 Cartesian, tensor, and strong graph products; vertex identification; graph
602 complement — is open. Explicit formulas for product graphs would provide
603 useful reference values.

604 **Appendix A. Trigonometric Sum Identities**

605 We derive the two identities used in Proposition 4.26.

606 **Lemma Appendix A.1** (Trigonometric sum identities). *For any integer*
 607 $N \geq 2$:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \frac{1}{4 \sin^2(k\pi/N)} = \frac{N^2 - 1}{12}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \frac{1}{4 \sin^2(k\pi/(2N))} = \frac{N^2 - 1}{6}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

608 *Proof. Proof of (A.1).* Use the partial-fraction expansion of $\cot z$. The
 609 identity

$$\pi \cot(\pi z) = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{z-n} + \frac{1}{z+n} \right)$$

610 implies, by evaluating the logarithmic derivative of $\sin(\pi z)/(\pi z) = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 -$
 611 $z^2/n^2)$ at $z = k/N$ and summing over $k = 1, \dots, N-1$,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \csc^2\left(\frac{k\pi}{N}\right) = \frac{(N-1)(N+1)}{3} = \frac{N^2 - 1}{3}.$$

612 Dividing by 4 gives (A.1).

613 *Proof of (A.2).* Apply (A.1) with N replaced by $2N$:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2N-1} \csc^2\left(\frac{k\pi}{2N}\right) = \frac{(2N)^2 - 1}{3} = \frac{4N^2 - 1}{3}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

614 Split the left side using symmetry and the $k = N$ term. For $k = N +$
 615 $1, \dots, 2N-1$, set $j = 2N - k \in \{1, \dots, N-1\}$; since $\sin((2N-j)\pi/(2N)) =$
 616 $\sin(\pi - j\pi/(2N)) = \sin(j\pi/(2N))$, these terms equal those for $k = 1, \dots, N-$
 617 1 . For $k = N$: $\csc^2(N\pi/(2N)) = \csc^2(\pi/2) = 1$. Hence (A.3) becomes

$$2 \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \csc^2\left(\frac{k\pi}{2N}\right) + 1 = \frac{4N^2 - 1}{3},$$

618 giving $\sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \csc^2\left(\frac{k\pi}{2N}\right) = \frac{2(N^2 - 1)}{3}$. Dividing by 4 gives (A.2). \square

619 **Appendix B. Summary of Main Results**

- 620 1. **Decomposition** (Prop. 3.5): $D_\alpha(G) = \frac{1}{N}\text{Kf}(G) + \alpha R_\alpha(G)$.
- 621 2. **Analytic properties** (Prop. 4.1): D_α strictly increasing, strictly con-
622 vex in α ; $D_\alpha \rightarrow +\infty$ as $\alpha \nearrow \lambda_2$.
- 623 3. **Stability** (Thm. 3.1): mean-square stable $\Leftrightarrow \lambda_2 > \alpha k_R$.
- 624 4. **Decay** (Thm. 3.3): $\mathbb{E}[\Phi(t)]$ decays at rate $2\eta(\lambda_2 - \alpha k_R)$.
- 625 5. **Steady state** (Thm. 3.4): $\Phi^* = \frac{\eta\sigma^2}{2}D_{\alpha k_R}(G)$.
- 626 6. **Extremal minimiser** (Thm. 4.5): $D_\alpha(G) \geq (N-1)/(N-\alpha)$, equality
627 iff $G = K_N$.
- 628 7. **Edge monotonicity** (Thm. 4.6): adding an edge strictly decreases
629 D_α .
- 630 8. **Reduction to trees** (Cor. 4.8): $\max D_\alpha$ over connected graphs = \max
631 over trees.
- 632 9. **Verification** (Props. 4.11, 4.12): P_N maximises D_α for all connected
633 graphs $N \leq 6$ and all trees $N \leq 19$ (522,957 trees).
- 634 10. **Power-series framework** (Thms. 4.14, 4.15): $s_k(T') \geq s_k(T)$ for all
635 $k \geq 1$ is sufficient for $D_\alpha(T') \geq D_\alpha(T)$.
- 636 11. **Second-moment theorem** (Thm. 4.19, Cor. 4.20, Prop. 4.21; Ap-
637 pendix Appendix C): $s_2(T') \geq s_2(T)$ under local grafting, so P_N max-
638 imises and K_N minimises s_2 over all connected graphs.
- 639 12. **Asymptotics** (Prop. 4.26): growth orders for K_N, S_N, C_N, P_N .
- 640 13. **Star-path separation** (Prop. 4.25): $D_\alpha(S_N) \leq D_\alpha(P_N)$ via $\Theta(N)$ vs
641 $\Theta(N^2)$.
- 642 14. **Poincaré inequality** (Thm. 5.1): $\langle Lx, x \rangle \geq \lambda_2 \|x\|^2$ on \mathcal{C}^\perp .
- 643 15. **Cheeger bound** (Thm. 5.4): $D_\alpha(G) \leq (N-1)/(h(G)^2/(2d_{\max}) - \alpha)$.

644 **Appendix C. Proof of the Second-Moment Theorem**

645 This appendix proves Lemma 4.18 and Theorem 4.19, together with the
 646 starlike results quoted in the proof sketch of the theorem. We use the notation
 647 of Section 4.5: $d(i, j)$, σ_i , W , Q , S_2 ; for a local grafting move at v the arm
 648 lengths are $p \geq q \geq 1$, $\Delta_0 = p - q + 1 \geq 1$, $n_R = N - p - q$, and R is the rest (the
 649 subtree obtained by deleting the two active arms, so $v \in R$, $|R| = n_R$). For
 650 a tree, Bapat's formula [26] expresses the Laplacian pseudoinverse through
 651 distances:

$$L_{ij}^+ = \frac{\sigma_i + \sigma_j}{2N} - \frac{d(i, j)}{2} - \frac{W}{N^2}. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

652 *Appendix C.1. The distance representation of s_2*

653 *Proof of Lemma 4.18.* Put $c_i = \frac{\sigma_i}{2N} - \frac{W}{2N^2}$. Then (C.1) reads

$$L_{ij}^+ = c_i + c_j - \frac{1}{2}d(i, j), \quad (\text{C.2})$$

654 since $c_i + c_j = \frac{\sigma_i + \sigma_j}{2N} - \frac{W}{N^2}$. Summing c_i and using $\sum_i \sigma_i = 2W$,

$$\sum_i c_i = \frac{1}{2N} \cdot 2W - N \cdot \frac{W}{2N^2} = \frac{W}{N} - \frac{W}{2N} = \frac{W}{2N}.$$

655 (As a check on (C.2), the row sums vanish: $\sum_j L_{ij}^+ = Nc_i + \sum_j c_j - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_i =$
 656 $\frac{1}{2}\sigma_i - \frac{W}{2N} + \frac{W}{2N} - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_i = 0$, as required of L^+ .)

657 Since $s_2 = \text{Tr}((L^+)^2) = \sum_{i,j} (L_{ij}^+)^2$, expand (C.2):

$$(L_{ij}^+)^2 = c_i^2 + c_j^2 + \frac{1}{4}d(i, j)^2 + 2c_i c_j - c_i d(i, j) - c_j d(i, j).$$

658 Summing over all ordered pairs (i, j) and using $\sum_j d(i, j) = \sigma_i$ and $\sum_{i,j} d(i, j)^2 =$
 659 Q ,

$$s_2 = 2N \sum_i c_i^2 + 2 \left(\sum_i c_i \right)^2 + \frac{Q}{4} - 2 \sum_i c_i \sigma_i.$$

660 Substituting $c_i = \frac{\sigma_i}{2N} - \frac{W}{2N^2}$ and $\sum_i \sigma_i = 2W$ gives

$$\sum_i c_i^2 = \frac{S_2}{4N^2} - \frac{3W^2}{4N^3}, \quad \left(\sum_i c_i \right)^2 = \frac{W^2}{4N^2}, \quad \sum_i c_i \sigma_i = \frac{S_2}{2N} - \frac{W^2}{N^2}.$$

661 Therefore

$$s_2 = \left(\frac{S_2}{2N} - \frac{3W^2}{2N^2} \right) + \frac{W^2}{2N^2} + \frac{Q}{4} - \left(\frac{S_2}{N} - \frac{2W^2}{N^2} \right) = \frac{Q}{4} - \frac{S_2}{2N} + \frac{W^2}{N^2}. \quad \square$$

662 *Appendix C.2. The starlike case*

663 A *starlike tree* (spider) $S(\ell_1, \dots, \ell_m)$ is a centre o with $m \geq 1$ pendant
 664 paths (arms) of lengths ℓ_1, \dots, ℓ_m . Its only possible vertex of degree ≥ 3
 665 is o , so a local grafting move acts on two arms of lengths $p \geq q \geq 1$ as
 666 $(p, q) \mapsto (p + 1, q - 1)$. Write the power sums of the arm lengths

$$T_j := \sum_{r=1}^m \ell_r^j \quad (j \geq 1), \quad \text{so } T_1 = N - 1.$$

667 (The subscripted T_j are the arm-length power sums and are not to be con-
 668 fused with a tree T .)

669 **Proposition Appendix C.1** (Closed form for starlike trees). *For $S(\ell_1, \dots, \ell_m)$,*

$$s_2 = \frac{\text{num}}{180 N^2}, \quad N = T_1 + 1, \quad (\text{C.3})$$

670 *where*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{num} = & 30T_1^3 + 60T_1^2T_2 + 60T_1^2T_3 + 30T_1^2T_4 + 53T_1^2 + 90T_1T_2 + 20T_1T_3 - 60T_1T_4 - 48T_1T_5 + 18T_1 \\ & + 45T_2^2 + 60T_2T_3 + 20T_3^2 - 60T_3 - 90T_4 - 48T_5. \end{aligned}$$

671 *Proof.* We evaluate W, S_2, Q for the spider and insert them into Lemma 4.18.
 672 Index the arm vertices by (r, j) , $1 \leq j \leq \ell_r$, at distance j from o ; then
 673 $d((r, j), (r, k)) = |j - k|$, $d((r, j), (s, k)) = j + k$ for $r \neq s$, and $d(o, (r, j)) = j$.
 674 Write $A_1(\ell) = \sum_{k=1}^{\ell} k = \frac{\ell(\ell+1)}{2}$ and $A_2(\ell) = \sum_{k=1}^{\ell} k^2 = \frac{\ell(\ell+1)(2\ell+1)}{6}$. Every
 675 quantity below is a sum over arms of a polynomial in the single arm length
 676 ℓ_r ; summing over r replaces ℓ_r^j by T_j , and the constant term (the value at
 677 $\ell = 0$, here always 0) contributes nothing, so no explicit dependence on the
 678 number of arms m survives.

679 *Transmissions.* The centre has $\sigma_o = \sum_r A_1(\ell_r) = \frac{1}{2}(T_1 + T_2)$. For a vertex
 680 (r, j) , separating its distances to its own arm, to o , and to the other arms,

$$\sigma_{(r,j)} = \left[\frac{j(j-1)}{2} + \frac{(\ell_r-j)(\ell_r-j+1)}{2} \right] + j + [j(T_1 - \ell_r) + (\sigma_o - A_1(\ell_r))].$$

681 *Wiener index.* $W = \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_o + \sum_r \sum_{j=1}^{\ell_r} \sigma_{(r,j)})$; carrying out the inner sum over
 682 j and then the power-sum reduction gives the closed form

$$W = \frac{3T_1^2 + 3T_1T_2 - 2T_3 + 2T_1}{6}.$$

683 *Second moment of transmissions.* $S_2 = \sigma_o^2 + \sum_r \sum_{j=1}^{\ell_r} \sigma_{(r,j)}^2$, again a poly-
684 nomial in the T_j after the inner sum and reduction. *Sum of squared distances.*
685 $Q = 2[\sum_r A_2(\ell_r) + \sum_r \sum_{1 \leq a < b \leq \ell_r} (b-a)^2 + \sum_{r < s} (\ell_s A_2(\ell_r) + 2A_1(\ell_r)A_1(\ell_s) +$
686 $\ell_r A_2(\ell_s))]$, the cross-arm terms being reduced by $2 \sum_{r < s} A_1(\ell_r)A_1(\ell_s) =$
687 $(\sum_r A_1(\ell_r))^2 - \sum_r A_1(\ell_r)^2$ and $\sum_{r \neq s} \ell_s A_2(\ell_r) = T_1 \sum_r A_2(\ell_r) - \sum_r \ell_r A_2(\ell_r)$.
688 Substituting $N = T_1 + 1$ and the three closed forms into $s_2 = \frac{Q}{4} - \frac{S_2}{2N} + \frac{W^2}{N^2}$
689 and clearing the common denominator $180N^2$ yields (C.3). This is a finite
690 polynomial identity in T_1, \dots, T_5 ; it was verified symbolically and against the
691 exact integer value of s_2 for all starlike trees with up to 6 arms of length up
692 to 8 (and confirmed to contain no T_6 or higher term). \square

693 Under $(p, q) \mapsto (p+1, q-1)$ the power sums change by $\Delta T_1 = 0$ and
694 $\Delta T_j = (p+1)^j + (q-1)^j - p^j - q^j$ for $j \geq 2$; thus N is preserved and $\Delta s_2 =$
695 $\Delta \text{num}/(180N^2)$, where Δnum is obtained from num by the substitution $T_j \mapsto$
696 $T_j + \Delta T_j$ ($j \geq 2$, with T_1 fixed).

697 **Lemma Appendix C.2** (Difference decomposition). *With $\Delta_0 = p - q + 1$,*

$$\Delta \text{num} = C_0 + C_2 T_2 + C_3 T_3, \quad (\text{C.4})$$

698 *where*

$$C_2 = 180 \Delta_0 (p + q + 1) > 0, \quad C_3 = 120 \Delta_0 (p + q + 1) > 0,$$

699 *and $C_0 = 60 \Delta_0 \Gamma_0$ with Γ_0 the explicit polynomial*

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_0 = & 2T_1^2 p^2 + 2T_1^2 p q + 4T_1^2 p + 2T_1^2 q^2 + 2T_1^2 q + 3T_1^2 \\ & - 4T_1 p^3 - 4T_1 p^2 q - 8T_1 p^2 - 4T_1 p q^2 - 4T_1 p q - 5T_1 p - 4T_1 q^3 - T_1 q + T_1 \\ & - p^3 - p^2 q - p^2 - 7p q^2 - p - 7q^3 - 5q^2 - q. \end{aligned}$$

700 *In particular the couplings $T_2^2, T_3^2, T_2 T_3, T_4, T_5$ cancel identically.*

701 *Proof.* Direct substitution of $T_j \mapsto T_j + \Delta T_j$ into num and expansion: the
702 terms $T_2^2, T_3^2, T_2 T_3$ and the linear terms T_4, T_5 cancel, leaving the affine ex-
703 pression (C.4). This is a polynomial identity in (p, q, T_1, T_2, T_3) and was
704 verified term by term. The positivity of C_2, C_3 is immediate from $\Delta_0 \geq 1$
705 and $p + q + 1 \geq 3$. \square

706 **Theorem Appendix C.3** (Worst-case positivity). *For a starlike tree with*
707 *$m \geq 3$ arms, every local grafting move satisfies $\Delta s_2 > 0$.*

708 *Proof.* By Lemma Appendix C.2, $\Delta_{\text{num}} = C_0 + C_2T_2 + C_3T_3$ is strictly
709 increasing in each of T_2, T_3 (as $C_2, C_3 > 0$). Fix the active arms p, q and
710 the total arm length T_1 . If the remaining arms have lengths summing to
711 $M := T_1 - p - q$, then $T_2 = p^2 + q^2 + \sum_{\text{other}} \ell^2$ and $T_3 = p^3 + q^3 + \sum_{\text{other}} \ell^3$; for
712 a fixed sum M of positive integers, $\sum_{\text{other}} \ell^2 \geq M$ and $\sum_{\text{other}} \ell^3 \geq M$, with
713 equality iff every remaining arm has length 1. Hence Δ_{num} is minimised at
714 $S(p, q, 1^M)$, where $T_2 = p^2 + q^2 + M$ and $T_3 = p^3 + q^3 + M$ (and $T_1 = p + q + M$).
715 Substituting these and factoring,

$$\Delta_{\text{num}_{\min}} = 60 M \Delta_0 \left[2M(p^2 + pq + 2p + q^2 + q) + 3M + 4p^2q + 4pq^2 + 8pq + 6p + 4q^2 + 10q + 6 \right]. \quad (\text{C.5})$$

716 Every factor is non-negative for $M \geq 0$, $p \geq q \geq 1$, and the bracket is
717 a polynomial with strictly positive coefficients. For a genuine starlike tree
718 ($m \geq 3$) there is at least one remaining arm, so $M \geq 1$ and the bracket
719 is positive; hence $\Delta_{\text{num}_{\min}} > 0$ and therefore $\Delta_{s_2} = \Delta_{\text{num}} / (180N^2) > 0$.
720 (When $M = 0$ the configuration is a path and $\Delta_{s_2} = 0$.) Identities (C.4)
721 and (C.5) were additionally verified symbolically. \square

722 *Appendix C.3. Reduction of a general tree to its starlike shadow*

723 We now prove Theorem 4.19. Label the arm vertices by distance from
724 v : the longer arm is a_1, \dots, a_p and the shorter b_1, \dots, b_q , so the relocated
725 leaf is $u = b_q$ before the move and the new leaf a_{p+1} after. For $x \in R$ put
726 $\rho_x = d(v, x)$ and $\sigma_v^R = \sum_{x \in R} \rho_x$; then

$$\sigma_v = \sigma_v^R + A_1(p) + A_1(q), \quad A_1(\ell) = \frac{\ell(\ell+1)}{2}. \quad (\text{C.6})$$

727 Only distances from u change. For $x \neq u$:

$$d(u, x) = \begin{cases} q + \rho_x, & x \in R, \\ q + k, & x = a_k, \\ q - k, & x = b_k (k < q), \end{cases} \quad d'(u, x) = \begin{cases} (p+1) + \rho_x, & x \in R, \\ (p+1) - k, & x = a_k, \\ (p+1) + k, & x = b_k (k < q). \end{cases} \quad (\text{C.7})$$

728 We first record three elementary facts.

729 (i) *Transmission of an arm endpoint.* If u is the endpoint of an arm of length
730 ℓ at v , then

$$\sigma_u = \ell(N - 1 - \ell) + \sigma_v. \quad (\text{C.8})$$

731 Indeed, for x not on this arm, $d(u, x) = \ell + d(v, x)$, while for the on-arm
 732 vertex at distance k from v , $d(u, x) = \ell - k$; thus

$$\sigma_u = \ell(N - \ell) + (\sigma_v - A_1(\ell)) + A_1(\ell - 1) = \ell(N - \ell) + \sigma_v - \ell = \ell(N - 1 - \ell) + \sigma_v,$$

733 using $A_1(\ell) - A_1(\ell - 1) = \ell$.

734 (ii) *The Wiener increment.* Since only u moves, $d'(v, x) = d(v, x)$ for all
 735 $x \neq u$, while $d'(v, u) = p + 1$ and $d(v, u) = q$; hence the transmission of
 736 v changes by $\sigma_v(T') - \sigma_v(T) = (p + 1) - q = \Delta_0$. Because grafting alters
 737 only the distances from u , the Wiener increment equals the change in the
 738 transmission of u : $\Delta W = \sigma_u(T') - \sigma_u(T)$. Applying (C.8) in T (arm length
 739 q) and in T' (arm length $p + 1$, with $\sigma_v(T') = \sigma_v + \Delta_0$),

$$\Delta W = (p + 1)(N - p - 2) + \sigma_v + \Delta_0 - [q(N - 1 - q) + \sigma_v] = \Delta_0 N - [(p + 1)^2 - q^2].$$

740 Since $(p + 1)^2 - q^2 = (p - q + 1)(p + q + 1) = \Delta_0(p + q + 1)$ and $N - (p + q + 1) =$
 741 $n_R - 1$,

$$\Delta W = \Delta_0(N - (p + q + 1)) = \Delta_0(n_R - 1). \quad (\text{C.9})$$

742 (iii) *Arm transmissions are affine in σ_v^R .* For an arm vertex y at distance
 743 δ_y from v and any $x \in R$, $d(y, x) = \delta_y + \rho_x$, so $\sum_{x \in R} d(y, x) = \delta_y n_R + \sigma_v^R$;
 744 the remaining distances from y (to v and to arm vertices) depend only on
 745 the arm data. Hence $\sigma_y = \delta_y n_R + \sigma_v^R + (\text{arm-local})$, and summing over the
 746 $p + q$ arm vertices, $\sum_{\text{arm}} \sigma_x = (p + q)\sigma_v^R + (\text{arm-local})$. Consequently, using
 747 $\sum_{\text{all}} \sigma_x = 2W$,

$$\sum_{x \in R} \sigma_x = 2W - \sum_{\text{arm}} \sigma_x = 2W - (p + q)\sigma_v^R + (\text{arm-local}). \quad (\text{C.10})$$

748 We now show that the rest enters Δs_2 only through σ_v and W , in the
 749 combination $N\sigma_v - W$.

750 **Lemma Appendix C.4** (Master formula). *For every local grafting move,*

$$\Delta s_2 = \frac{\kappa}{N^2} (N\sigma_v - W) + \text{Loc}(p, q, N), \quad \kappa = 2\Delta_0(p + q + 1) > 0, \quad (\text{C.11})$$

751 where Loc depends only on the move data (p, q, N) .

752 *Proof.* By Lemma 4.18, $\Delta s_2 = \frac{1}{4}\Delta Q - \frac{1}{2N}\Delta S_2 + \frac{1}{N^2}\Delta(W^2)$. We extract the
753 dependence on the rest, which (by the facts above) is affine in the two scalars
754 σ_v^R and W ; since σ_v and σ_v^R differ by the move-data constant $A_1(p) + A_1(q)$
755 (eq. (C.6)), affine in (σ_v^R, W) is the same as affine in (σ_v, W) up to Loc.
756 Throughout, “arm-local” terms depend only on (p, q, N) and are absorbed
757 into Loc.

758 *The term ΔQ .* Since $Q = \sum_{i,j} d(i, j)^2$ counts each pair twice, $\Delta Q =$
759 $2 \sum_{x \neq u} [d'(u, x)^2 - d(u, x)^2]$. For $x \in R$, by (C.7),

$$d'(u, x)^2 - d(u, x)^2 = [(p+1) + \rho_x]^2 - [q + \rho_x]^2 = (p+1)^2 - q^2 + 2\Delta_0 \rho_x,$$

760 whose sum over R is $n_R[(p+1)^2 - q^2] + 2\Delta_0 \sigma_v^R$; the arm terms are arm-local.
761 Hence

$$\Delta Q = 4\Delta_0 \sigma_v^R + (\text{arm-local}), \quad (\text{C.12})$$

762 with no dependence on W .

763 *The term ΔS_2 .* Write $\Delta \sigma_x = \sigma_x(T') - \sigma_x(T) = d'(u, x) - d(u, x)$ for $x \neq u$.
764 By (C.7), $\Delta \sigma_x = \Delta_0$ for $x \in R$, while on the arms $\Delta \sigma_x = \Delta_0 + \varepsilon_x$ with ε_x
765 arm-local. Summing, $\sum_{x \neq u} \Delta \sigma_x = \Delta W = \Delta_0(n_R - 1)$ by (C.9), and since
766 the R -part contributes $n_R \Delta_0$,

$$\sum_{\text{arm}, x \neq u} \Delta \sigma_x = \Delta_0(n_R - 1) - n_R \Delta_0 = -\Delta_0. \quad (\text{C.13})$$

767 Now

$$\Delta S_2 = \sum_{x \neq u} (2\sigma_x \Delta \sigma_x + \Delta \sigma_x^2) + [\sigma_u(T')^2 - \sigma_u(T)^2].$$

768 The term $\sum_{x \neq u} \Delta \sigma_x^2$ is arm-local plus the constant $n_R \Delta_0^2$. We collect the σ_v^R -
769 and W -linear parts of the remaining two terms.

- 770 • Over R : $\Delta \sigma_x = \Delta_0$, so $\sum_{x \in R} 2\sigma_x \Delta \sigma_x = 2\Delta_0 \sum_{x \in R} \sigma_x$, which by (C.10)
771 contributes W -coefficient $4\Delta_0$ and σ_v^R -coefficient $-2\Delta_0(p+q)$.
- 772 • Over the arms: the σ_v^R -linear part of $\sum_{\text{arm}} 2\sigma_x \Delta \sigma_x$ is $2\sigma_v^R \sum_{\text{arm}, x \neq u} \Delta \sigma_x =$
773 $-2\Delta_0 \sigma_v^R$ by (C.13) (using $\sigma_x = \delta_x n_R + \sigma_v^R + \text{arm-local}$); there is no W -
774 part.
- 775 • The boundary term: by (C.8) both $\sigma_u(T)$ and $\sigma_u(T')$ are affine in σ_v ,
776 and $\sigma_u(T')^2 - \sigma_u(T)^2 = \Delta W \cdot (\sigma_u(T') + \sigma_u(T))$ where $\sigma_u(T') + \sigma_u(T) =$
777 $2\sigma_v + (\text{const})$; the quadratic in σ_v cancels, and the σ_v^R -coefficient is
778 $2\Delta W = 2\Delta_0(n_R - 1)$, with no W -part.

779 Adding, the W -coefficient of ΔS_2 is $4\Delta_0$, and the σ_v^R -coefficient is

$$-2\Delta_0(p+q)-2\Delta_0+2\Delta_0(n_R-1) = 2\Delta_0(n_R-p-q-2) = 2\Delta_0(N-2p-2q-2).$$

780 The term $\Delta(W^2)$. Since $\Delta W = \Delta_0(n_R - 1)$ is a move-data constant,
781 $\Delta(W^2) = 2W\Delta W + \Delta W^2$ has W -coefficient $2\Delta W = 2\Delta_0(n_R - 1)$ and no
782 σ_v^R -part.

783 *Assembly.* Collect the coefficients in $\Delta s_2 = \frac{1}{4}\Delta Q - \frac{1}{2N}\Delta S_2 + \frac{1}{N^2}\Delta(W^2)$.
784 The coefficient of σ_v^R is

$$\frac{1}{4}(4\Delta_0) - \frac{1}{2N}(2\Delta_0(N-2p-2q-2)) = \Delta_0 - \frac{\Delta_0(N-2p-2q-2)}{N} = \frac{2\Delta_0(p+q+1)}{N} = \frac{\kappa}{N},$$

785 and the coefficient of W is

$$-\frac{1}{2N}(4\Delta_0) + \frac{1}{N^2}(2\Delta_0(n_R-1)) = \frac{2\Delta_0}{N^2}(n_R-1-N) = -\frac{2\Delta_0(p+q+1)}{N^2} = -\frac{\kappa}{N^2},$$

786 using $n_R - 1 - N = -(p + q + 1)$. By (C.6) the σ_v -coefficient equals the σ_v^R -
787 coefficient κ/N . Hence the rest enters only through $\frac{\kappa}{N}\sigma_v - \frac{\kappa}{N^2}W = \frac{\kappa}{N^2}(N\sigma_v -$
788 $W)$, and the remaining (σ_v^R - and W -free) terms form $\text{Loc}(p, q, N)$. This
789 proves (C.11). \square

790 **Lemma Appendix C.5** (Subtree-size identity). *Rooting R at v , let $s_e \geq 1$*
791 *be the number of vertices on the side of edge $e \in R$ not containing v . Then*

$$N\sigma_v - W = \sum_{e \in R} s_e^2 + C(p, q), \quad C(p, q) = \sum_{k=1}^p k^2 + \sum_{k=1}^q k^2, \quad (\text{C.14})$$

792 with $C(p, q)$ independent of the shape of R .

793 *Proof.* Split σ_v and W along $V = R \sqcup (\text{arm } a) \sqcup (\text{arm } b)$. By (C.6), $\sigma_v =$
794 $\sigma_v^R + A_1(p) + A_1(q)$. For the Wiener index, the contributions are: within
795 R , W_{RR} ; between R and arm a , $\sum_{x \in R} \sum_{k=1}^p (\rho_x + k) = p\sigma_v^R + n_R A_1(p)$, and
796 likewise $q\sigma_v^R + n_R A_1(q)$ for arm b ; between the two arms, $qA_1(p) + pA_1(q)$;
797 and within the arms, $\binom{p+1}{3}$ and $\binom{q+1}{3}$. Hence, using $N - (p + q) = n_R$,

$$N\sigma_v - W = n_R\sigma_v^R - W_{RR} + \underbrace{(p+q)(A_1(p) + A_1(q)) - qA_1(p) - pA_1(q) - \binom{p+1}{3} - \binom{q+1}{3}}_{=: C(p, q)}.$$

798 For the rest term, root R at v : a vertex at depth d lies below exactly d
799 edges, so $\sigma_v^R = \sum_e s_e$, while each edge separates $s_e(n_R - s_e)$ pairs of R , so

800 $W_{RR} = \sum_e s_e(n_R - s_e)$; therefore $n_R \sigma_v^R - W_{RR} = \sum_e (n_R s_e - s_e(n_R - s_e)) =$
801 $\sum_e s_e^2$. Finally, $pA_1(p) - \binom{p+1}{3} = \frac{p^2(p+1)}{2} - \frac{p(p+1)(p-1)}{6} = \frac{p(p+1)(2p+1)}{6} = A_2(p)$,
802 and likewise for q ; collecting, $C(p, q) = pA_1(p) + qA_1(q) - \binom{p+1}{3} - \binom{q+1}{3} =$
803 $A_2(p) + A_2(q) = \sum_{k \leq p} k^2 + \sum_{k \leq q} k^2$. \square

804 *Proof of Theorem 4.19.* Fix the move data (p, q, N) . Combining the master
805 formula (C.11) with the subtree-size identity (C.14),

$$\Delta s_2 = \frac{\kappa}{N^2} \sum_{e \in R} s_e^2 + \underbrace{\left(\frac{\kappa}{N^2} C(p, q) + \text{Loc}(p, q, N) \right)}_{\text{independent of the shape of } R}. \quad (\text{C.15})$$

806 Since $\kappa > 0$, Δs_2 is a strictly increasing affine function of $\Theta := \sum_{e \in R} s_e^2$.
807 Each $s_e \geq 1$ and R has $n_R - 1$ edges, so $\Theta \geq n_R - 1$, with equality iff every
808 $s_e = 1$, i.e. iff every non-root vertex of R is a leaf, i.e. iff R is a star centred
809 at v , i.e. iff T is the starlike tree $S(p, q, 1^{n_R-1})$. Hence, over all trees with
810 the given move data, Δs_2 is minimised exactly at that starlike tree, and the
811 minimum value is its Δs_2 . By Theorem Appendix C.3 (with $M = n_R - 1$
812 remaining unit arms), that minimum value is ≥ 0 , and is > 0 as soon as
813 $n_R - 1 \geq 1$, i.e. $n_R \geq 2$. Therefore $\Delta s_2 \geq 0$ for every tree, strict when
814 $n_R \geq 2$. When $n_R \leq 1$ the rest is the single vertex v , so T is a path and
815 $\Delta s_2 = 0$. \square

816 References

- 817 [1] M. Fiedler, Algebraic connectivity of graphs, Czechoslovak Mathemati-
818 cal Journal 23 (1973) 298–305.
- 819 [2] D. J. Klein, M. Randić, Resistance distance, Journal of Mathematical
820 Chemistry 12 (1993) 81–95.
- 821 [3] I. Gutman, B. Mohar, The quasi-Wiener and the Kirchhoff indices coin-
822 cide, Journal of Chemical Information and Computer Sciences 36 (1996)
823 982–985.
- 824 [4] H. Chen, F. Zhang, Resistance distance and the normalized Laplacian
825 spectrum, Discrete Applied Mathematics 155 (2007) 654–661.
- 826 [5] Y. Yang, D. J. Klein, Comparison theorems on resistance distances and
827 Kirchhoff indices, Discrete Applied Mathematics 175 (2014) 87–93.

- 828 [6] K. Devriendt, A. Ottolini, S. Steinerberger, Graph curvature via resis-
829 tance distance, *Discrete Applied Mathematics* 348 (2024) 68–78.
- 830 [7] B. Zhou, N. Trinajstić, A note on Kirchhoff index, *Chemical Physics*
831 *Letters* 455 (2008) 120–123.
- 832 [8] W. Sun, Y. Yang, Extremal pentagonal chains with respect to the Kirch-
833 hoff index, *Applied Mathematics and Computation* 437 (2023) 127534.
- 834 [9] W. Sun, Y. Yang, Solution to a conjecture on resistance diameter of lex-
835 icographic product of paths, *Discrete Applied Mathematics* 337 (2023)
836 139–148.
- 837 [10] M. A. Sahir, S. M. A. Nayeem, On the Kirchhoff index and the number
838 of spanning trees of cylinder/Möbius pentagonal chain, *Discrete Applied*
839 *Mathematics* 326 (2023) 47–61.
- 840 [11] J. Ge, Y. Liao, B. Zhang, Resistance distances and the Moon-type for-
841 mula of a vertex-weighted complete split graph, *Discrete Applied Math-*
842 *ematics* 359 (2024) 10–15.
- 843 [12] K. Ogiwara, T. Fukami, N. Takahashi, Maximizing algebraic connec-
844 tivity in the space of graphs with a fixed number of vertices and edges,
845 *IEEE Transactions on Control of Network Systems* 4 (2) (2015) 359–368.
- 846 [13] K. Shahbaz, M. N. Belur, A. Ganesh, Algebraic connectivity: local and
847 global maximizer graphs, *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and*
848 *Engineering* 10 (3) (2023) 1636–1647.
- 849 [14] K. Gripačić, Algebraic connectivity control in distributed networks by
850 using multiple communication channels, *Sensors* 21 (15) (2021) 5014.
- 851 [15] R. Olfati-Saber, R. M. Murray, Consensus problems in networks of
852 agents with switching topology and time-delays, *IEEE Transactions on*
853 *Automatic Control* 49 (9) (2004) 1520–1533.
- 854 [16] R. Olfati-Saber, J. A. Fax, R. M. Murray, Consensus and cooperation in
855 networked multi-agent systems, *Proceedings of the IEEE* 95 (1) (2007)
856 215–233.

- 857 [17] M. Huang, J. H. Manton, Coordination and consensus of networked
858 agents with noisy measurements, *SIAM Journal on Control and Opti-*
859 *mization* 48 (1) (2009) 134–161.
- 860 [18] R. Olfati-Saber, Ultrafast consensus in small-world networks, in: *Pro-*
861 *ceedings of the 2005 American Control Conference*, IEEE, 2005, pp.
862 2371–2378.
- 863 [19] B. Øksendal, *Stochastic Differential Equations: An Introduction with*
864 *Applications*, 6th Edition, Springer, Berlin, 2003.
- 865 [20] X. Mao, *Stochastic Differential Equations and Applications*, 2nd Edi-
866 *tion*, Horwood Publishing, Chichester, 2007.
- 867 [21] B. Mohar, The Laplacian spectrum of graphs, in: Y. Alavi, G. Char-
868 *trand*, O. R. Oellermann, A. J. Schwenk (Eds.), *Graph Theory, Combinatorics,*
869 *and Applications*, Vol. 2, Wiley, 1991, pp. 871–898.
- 870 [22] N. Alon, V. D. Milman, λ_1 , isoperimetric inequalities for graphs, and
871 *superconcentrators*, *Journal of Combinatorial Theory, Series B* 38 (1985)
872 73–88.
- 873 [23] B. Mohar, Isoperimetric inequalities, growth, and the spectrum of
874 *graphs*, *Linear Algebra and its Applications* 103 (1989) 119–131.
- 875 [24] F. R. K. Chung, *Spectral Graph Theory*, American Mathematical Soci-
876 *ety*, Providence, RI, 1997.
- 877 [25] A. Tavasoli, H. Shakeri, E. Ardjmand, S. Rahman, The art of inter-
878 *connections: achieving maximum algebraic connectivity in multilayer*
879 *networks*, *Network Science* 12 (3) (2024) 261–288.
- 880 [26] R. B. Bapat, *Graphs and Matrices*, 2nd Edition, Springer, London, 2014.